

Use Case Requirements

Deliverable 2.3

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Document details

Project Acronym/ Name:	ORION/ Novel Digital Components for International renewable energy value chains
Project URL:	https://he-orion.eu/
Project Type:	HORIZON Research and Innovation Action
EU CALL:	HORIZON-CL5-2023-D3-03
Grant Agreement No.:	101158432
Project Start Date:	01/09/2024
Project End Date:	31/08/2027
Workpackage:	2
Deliverable:	2.3
Due date of Deliverable:	28/02/2025
Actual Submission Date:	29/04/2025
Name of Lead Beneficiary for this deliverable:	EDP CNET
Reviewed by:	AUGM
Revision:	22/04/2025
Dissemination Level:	PU

Document History

Version	Date	Comment	Modifications made by
0.1	24/09/2024	Sent the UCs template to all partners	EDP
0.1	15/01/2025	Provided contributions from all partners to the UCs template	EDP
0.1	28/01/2025	Initial Version of the Literature Review	INESC
0.1	10/02/2025	Partner Contributions Included	INESC
0.1	14/02/2025	All sections included and merge of state of the art and UCs description	EDP
0.1	11/04/2025	Draft for partners and quality review	EDP
0.2	22/04/2025	Document reviewed	EDP, AUGM, Use Case partners
0.3	29/04/2025	Revision implemented	EDP
1.0	29/04/2025	Final document delivered	SINTEF

Disclaimer

Any dissemination of results reflects only the author's view and neither the European Commission nor the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) is responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Copyright message

© Partners of the Consortium, 2031

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Acknowledgements

This deliverable was developed based on collective efforts from all partners of the consortium.

Glossary and Abbreviations

UC	Use Case
H2020	Horizon 2020
HE	Horizon Europe
GA	General Assembly
API	Application Programming Interface
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
WEC	Wave Energy Converters
CIM	Common Information Model
EPRI	Electric Power Research Institute
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
DT	Digital Twin
IoT	Internet of Things
DERs	Distributed Energy Resources
BIM	Building Information Models
TSO	Transmission System Operators
DSO	Distribution System Operators
SGTF	Smart Grids Task Force
CGMES	Common Grid Model Exchange Standard
EMS	Energy Management System
IMS	Intelligent Monitoring System
ML	Machine Learning
SOH	State of Health
MPC	Model Predictive Control
LCoE	Levelized Cost of Energy
BI-WECs	Built-in Wave Energy Converters
PTO	Power Take-Off
HIL	Hardware-In-The-Loop

CNNs	Convolutional Neural Networks
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
TENGs	Triboelectric Nanogenerators
ANNs	Artificial Neural Networks
BESSs	Battery Energy Storage Systems
CUSUM	Cumulative Sum
GB	Gradient Boosting
GNN	Graph Neural Network
GRUs	Gated Recurrent Units
KNNs	k-Nearest Neighbors
L-G	Line-to-Ground
L-L	Line-to-Line
NNs	Neural Networks
O&M	Operations and Maintenance
PV	Photovoltaic
PVPPs	Photovoltaic Power Plants
RCNN	Region Convolutional Neural Network
RFs	Random Forests
RGB	Red, Green, and Blue
RNN	Recurrent Neural Network
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
PQ	Power Quality
GD-RTDCS	Geographically Distributed Real-Time Digital Co-Simulation
ALFs	Adaptive Latent Features
WG	Working Group
UML	Unified Modeling Language
TFD	Time-Frequency Domain
TD	Time Domain
SRF	Structural Rotor Fault
SMs	Submodules

SFs	Statistical Features
RDF	Resource Description Framework
NLM	Nearest Level Modulation
MPPT	Maximum Power Point Tracking
MMC	Multilevel Converter
LightGBM	Light Gradient Boosting Machine
ISCF	Inter-turn Short Circuit Fault
FT	Fault-Tolerant
FDL	Fault Detection and Localization
FD	Frequency Domain

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	9
1. Introduction	10
1.1. About the project	10
1.2. Objectives of D2.3.....	10
1.3. Targets of D2.3.....	11
1.4. Methodology.....	11
2. Use Cases Methodology	12
2.1. IEC 62559-2	12
2.2. Key Concepts.....	13
2.3. Use Cases' Template	13
3. Use Cases Description	16
3.1. Use Case 1: Norway and Cape Verde	16
3.2. Use Case 2: Portugal.....	21
3.3. Use Case 3: Slovenia.....	25
3.4. Use Case 4: Brazil.....	29
3.5. Use Case 5: Canada	32
4. State of the Art	36
4.1. Sensor Technologies	36
4.2. Data and model interoperability components	44
4.3. Digital asset information components	52
4.4. Data-driven decision systems components.....	56
5. State of the Art: Summary Tables	62
5.1. Sensor Technologies	62
5.2. Data and model interoperability components	64
5.3. Digital asset information components	66
5.4. Data-driven decision systems components.....	68
6. Strengths, Opportunities, and Shared Characteristics of the Use Cases	72
6.1. Strengths and Opportunities of Each Use Case	72
6.2. Common Features and Interconnections Across Use Cases	74
7. Conclusions and next steps	75
References	76

List of Figures

Figure 1 - Template to describe each Use Case.....	15
Figure 2 - Regional onshore and offshore wind outlook for new installations (GW). GWEC's Global Wind Report 2023 features the latest key statistics of the status report for the global wind industry. [2]	36
Figure 3 - Floating offshore wind turbines. The WindFloat Atlantic project, the first Offshore Wind Farm in Portugal installed on floating platforms. [4]	37
Figure 4 - Wave Energy Converter. AWS Ocean Energy, 16 kW Archimedes Waveswing wave energy converter. [5]	38
Figure 5 - Hardware-in-the-loop simulation of wave energy converters and power take-offs. Hardware-in-the-loop simulation methods for wave energy converters propose a classification framework based on simulated, real, and interface subsystems to improve organization and application. [9]	41
Figure 6 - Triboelectric Nanogenerators: devices that generate energy through waves. Researchers from IFIMUP, FEUP, and INEGI (Portugal) have developed three triboelectric nanogenerators that generate electricity from the movement of waves. The goal is to install them on ocean buoys to increase the operation time without human intervention. [13].....	43
Figure 7 - Power generation and greenhouse gas emissions in Europe. [52]	56
Figure 7 - Carbon Neutrality Roadmap 2050: The consolidated path to corporate sustainability [53]. The European Green Deal aims to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 55% by 2030, compared to 1990 levels, and achieve climate neutrality by 2050. The goals include increasing energy efficiency (by 32,5% by 2030), promoting renewable energy (by 42.5% by 2030).....	57
Figure 9 - Global Energy System Model (GENeSYS-MOD) [54]	58
Figure 10 - Model for decision making system [57]	59
Figure 11 - Interconnections Across Use Cases	74

List of Tables

Table 1 - Strengths and Opportunities for Use Case 1	72
Table 2 - Strengths and Opportunities for Use Case 2	72
Table 3 - Strengths and Opportunities for Use Case 3	73
Table 4 - Strengths and Opportunities for Use Case 4	73
Table 5 - Strengths and Opportunities for Use Case 5	73

Executive Summary

This document presents the deliverable ORION_D2.3 'Use Case Requirements' of the Horizon Europe project ORION. The present deliverable establishes a comprehensive guide for ORION's Use Cases (UC), providing an exhaustive analysis of each one of the 5 UCs, by describing all the interactions and actors involved in each one, detailing the analysis of the current state of the art and reporting the main strengths and weaknesses.

Furthermore, the document explores critical aspects of energy systems, sensor technologies, and data-driven decision-making structures that are involved in ORION's UCs. The primary objective is to thoroughly describe each UC (following IEC 62559-2 standard) and provide a comprehensive and state-of-the-art overview of the involved domains, emphasizing their relevance to contemporary challenges such as renewable energy integration, offshore system optimization, and energy system digitalization. Synthesizing information across various fields, the deliverable aims to enhance the understanding of complexities and opportunities for each UC.

To enrich the state of the art, the content has been carefully developed with insights drawn from the latest academic and industrial research, focusing on distinct yet interconnected topics. These additions ensure that the document reflects the most up-to-date knowledge and incorporates the latest advancements in the respective fields, grounded in specialized literature and within the scope of European projects.

Following the development of the initial version, the document will undergo a thorough review, including contributions from project partners who will critically assess the content, suggest improvements, and provide additional insights. Their feedback will enhance the technical depth and ensure alignment with project objectives. This iterative and collaborative approach aims to create a comprehensive and up-to-date resource, fostering a deeper understanding of current solutions and challenges.

1. Introduction

1.1. About the project

The ORION vision is to strengthen the European leadership in science and technology and accelerate the twin energy transition of the energy value chain stakeholders with a quintuple-helix model by delivering a modular toolbox of digital breakthrough components. Then, validating these components in the unique use cases of hydro, solar and wave energy operations across four continents, and integrating and presenting these novelties in human-centric Digital Twin applications, to enable a higher-degree of digitalisation of relevant operational and business processes. This is expected to increase the renewables share in the electricity grid globally and reduce fossil fuels consumption in the context of an increased demand for energy resources and uncertain geopolitical and climate conditions in the long term.

As part of ORION_T2.1 and ORION_T2.2, this document outlines ORION_D2.3 – Use Case Requirements, focusing on the details of the analysis of the current state of art of ORION technologies and reports technical strengths and weakness as well as UCs' demands for the digital components.

1.2. Objectives of D2.3

This deliverable was developed in the context of WP2, which has the following objectives:

- Comprehensive mapping of ORION technologies state-of-the-art as starting point for the project's own developments.
- Definition of ORION's overall architecture design, identifying needs and requirements for the interaction between the different layers and technologies and ensuring the interoperability and links to the five use cases.
- Ensure proper data governance, complying with GDPR and aligning with the relevant international regulations applicable to Cape Verde, Brazil and Canada.

This document focuses on the first two objectives of the deliverable, by addressing an in-depth analysis of ORION's technologies and thoroughly characterising each one of the 5 UCs, to further expand the knowledge and interactions that each UC should obey.

1.3. Targets of D2.3

This deliverable aims to address Tasks 2.1 and 2.2, Technical requirements analysis and state of the art and Use Case requirements, respectively. With this in mind, the deliverable aggregates the overall analysis for the state of the art for each UC, indicating the UCs' needs, actors and expectations as well, following a well-designed framework outlined in Chapter 2 of this deliverable.

1.4. Methodology

This document is divided into 7 main sections:

- I. Introduction
- II. Use Cases Methodology
- III. Use Cases Description
- IV. State of the Art
- V. State of the Art: Summary Tables
- VI. Strengths, Opportunities, and Shared Characteristics of the Use Cases
- VII. Conclusions

This deliverable represents an overview for each use case, both for the implementation but also for the analysis of each technology (benchmarking it against the state of the art). The tasks associated with this deliverable proceed until M12 and M18, for T2.1 and T2.2, respectively, thus the UCs will be revised and upgraded throughout these months. The outputs of this deliverable will be paramount for WP3 and WP4 activities.

2. Use Cases Methodology

This section outlines the methodology used to identify and describe each Use Case (UC) of the project. The methodology adopted by the ORION project adopts a well-established IEC on Use Cases' description, which has been used in several European (H2020 and HE) projects. With this methodology, each Use Case will clearly list the main objectives, the relevant stakeholders, the human and non-human involved actors in each UC. All UCs are herein presented in a well-structured template, fully describing and organizing the technical requirements of a specific operational activity. Following this procedure, the UC description should identify a set of potential interactions or actions performed by the system or between the different actors identified. Using this methodology, the UCs should be kept generic enough in terms of technological implementation to ensure minor adaptations (keeping the overall objectives intact) and timely replicability. The UCs present different levels of detail / granularity, in function of their objectives and goals (some UCs are more overarching than others).

2.1. IEC 62559-2

An international standard methodology to define and describe Use Cases (UCs), here named Case Studies, is proposed in the IEC 62559-2 norm, named Use Case Methodology – Definition of the templates for use cases, actor list and requirements list. IEC is an international organization that promotes cooperation concerning standardization in the electrical and electronic fields. The IEC 62559-2 norm also defines: (i) the key concepts and terminology associated with UC development (which creates the basis for a common repository of UCs); (ii) the essential structure for a UC, providing a comprehensive template for this effect; and (iii) a serialization method for the definition of UCs.

The project will leverage the template provided by the IEC norm to define the set of actions that will be developed and implemented during the course of the project. This will help to define high-level requirements and specifications for the first stages of project development, and contributing to the basis of the work being developed in the remaining time period. However, an adaptation of the template will be made in the context of this project since the IEC norm was created having in mind projects in the electrical and electronics field, while this project has a more overarching scope. Therefore, the structure of the UC template is divided in six main stages and can be described as follows:

- 1) Description of UC – The first stage of the template, which describes the UC as per its scope, objectives, related technical solutions and pilot site;

- 2) Stakeholders – List all the relevant stakeholders for the UC, characterizing its type (lead, primary, secondary) and sort of role;
- 3) Use Case conditions – Specify the pre and post requisites for the UC lifecycle;
- 4) Scenario List - List all scenarios of the UC, presenting a brief description;
- 5) Actors – This stage will be related with the identification of the actors involved in the UC and the description of their key role;
- 6) Information exchanged – The final stage of the template typifies and describes the information to be exchanged during and after the UC scenarios.

2.2. Key Concepts

The relevant terminology related with the UCs used throughout this document will be defined herein, in accordance with the definitions presented in the IEC norm. To understand and complete the UC template, it is essential to have a set of clear definitions of key concepts. Amongst all the definitions available in the IEC norm, we herein selected the most important ones – actor, scenario, information exchanged and prerequisite –, as evidenced below:

- An actor is as any entity that communicates and interacts with the various components needed to develop the UC. This concept can include humans, software applications, systems, databases;
- Information exchanged represents all the different types of data and input or output signals which need to be communicated between actors for the proper development of the UC;
- Prerequisites specify which requirements have to be met so that the basis scenario UC can be successfully accomplished – they often contain properties and states of actors, or the condition of a triggering event.

These key concepts have been successfully used by some of ORION partners in other HE projects.

2.3. Use Cases' Template

The process adopted to produce the most relevant content in this report has included all partners, with special focus on the UC owners and related technology partners. The UC definition process went through a set of iterations that may be described as follows:

- 1) Preparation of the UC template – A UC template was prepared, shown in Figure 1, (shown below) adopting the IEC recommendations, with the objective of having a common base to describe each UC. The UC template intends to be as technologically agnostic as possible.
- 2) Filling of UCs – The UCs were filled by the UC owners, following interactions with the technology experts, EDP and INESC.

- 3) UCs complete description – The UCs final description followed the interactions between UC owners, related technology experts, EDP, INESC, RWTH and AUGM (as WP3 and WP4 leaders). The final description followed the final adjustments discussed throughout ORION's 2nd GA.

UCX		Use Case Title
Description		
Short Description	Short description of the UC.	
Long Description	Long description of the UC.	
Objectives and Scope		
Objectives	Objectives of the UC	
Related Use Cases	Related UC	
Related ORION Objectives [section 1.1.1 of the GA]	Specify related ORION objectives	
Related ORION Technical Solutions [section 1.1.2 of the GA]	Specify related ORION technical solutions	
Pilot Sites	Identify the pilot site	
Stakeholders		
Name	Type	Role/Interest
Stakeholder X	List the Lead, primary and secondary stakeholders	Identify the role
Stakeholder Y
Use Case Conditions		
Prerequisites	Specify which requirements have to be met so that the basis scenario can be accomplished. They contain: - Properties and states of actors; - Condition(s) of a triggering event.	
Post requisites	Specify the condition after UC being operational	
Actors		
Name	Type	Role

XXX	Type could be: - Human; - Device; - Intelligent electronic device; - System; - External System; - Software; - ...	Describe the participatory role of the respective actor.
Scenario List		
List all scenarios. Each scenario should encompass: - Scenario title; - Brief description		
Information Exchanged		
Name	Type	Description
XXX	-Input; -Output; - Input / output;	Describe the type of signal and its format, including the parameters' range.
Additional Information		
Additional information relevant to the UC.		

Figure 1 - Template to describe each Use Case

3. Use Cases Description

3.1. Use Case 1: Norway and Cape Verde

The first Use Case address the pivotal role that Ports will play in Europe's decarbonisation agenda. This Use Case approach is the decarbonisation of port cities by increasing onshore RES share, mostly hydropower, for cruise ships in closed environments.

The complex cross-section of industries facilitated by and operating within ports has huge potential for significantly reducing Europe's greenhouse gas emissions and aiding the transition to clean energy. This use case has an intercontinental dimension because the ports from Norway and Cape Verde are twinning to jointly address the challenges.

Mindelo is a city in Cape Verde with an active port receiving multiple cruise ships, fishing vessels and cargo terminals incorporated. It has approximately 75,000 inhabitants spread over a total area of 67 km² in the northwest of the island of São Vicente. There is an urgent need to build an infrastructure to supply ships with shore power – for example by adding more RES to the grid, in order to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and align Cape Verde with international environmental policies.

UC1	Port Decarbonization – São Vicente Island
Description	
Short Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Improve the operational efficiency of the island with regard to reducing greenhouse gas emissions and optimizing energy use with a focus on electricity demand and renewable energy sources, integrating advanced DT (AUGM) and AI technologies (IMT)- Test and validate the developed components in the defined scenarios
Objectives and Scope	
Objectives	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Collection and enrichment of data from stakeholders and involved parties.2. Development of scenarios based on the data and challenges detailed on ORION Project.

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Test and validate the developed components in WP3 (via IMT) and recommendations for sizing, timing throughout the day to optimize energy use with a focus on electricity 4. Provide recommendations for energy demand and renewable energy sources considering sustainability and flexibility over time. 	
Related Use Cases	UC1 is a two-headed UC, thus synergies and interactions between Cape Verde and Norway islands will be natural.	
Related ORION Objectives [section 1.1.1]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - O3: Deliver data-driven decision system components to increase RES share with a focus on hydro energy in the local grid and reduce fossil fuels consumption in closed environments (ports); - O4: Advance AI-supported tools for operation and maintenance of large-scale solar energy plants to increase the energy availability and reliability (Task 3.4); - O5: Create, AUGMENTCITY AS develop and test the human-centric Digital Twin applications that are interoperable and implementable at different scales and use cases in order to provide the stakeholders with evidence-based information, support their decision making and enable best practise exchange globally (Task 3.5) 	
Related ORION Technical Solutions [section 1.1.2]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Human-centric Digital Twin applications (1.1.2.1) - Digital asset information components (1.1.2.4) 	
Pilot Sites	São Vicente Island, Cabo Verde (Bay of Porto Grande)	
Stakeholders		
Name	Type	Role/Interest
UTA	Leader	Link the Orion Project with the Capeverdean stakeholders, gather data from local stakeholders, support the partners in testing, validating the developed solutions, and provide recommendations for energy demand and renewable energy sources considering sustainability and flexibility over time.
AUGMENTCITY AS	Primary	Testing and Validation; Human-centric DT applications

IMT	Primary	Development of the AI and optimization algorithms that will optimise energy usage in order to reduce CO2 emissions
RWTH	Secondary	Cloud-based platform responsible for data harmonisation

Use Case Conditions

Prerequisites

1. Data availability (e.g. from SCADA systems)
2. Vessel name/engine characteristics (port information).
3. Power consumption at the shore station, and power consumption of EVs connected.
4. Weather (temperature, precipitation, irradiation).
5. Power generation data and water consumption data.
6. Other prerequisites may be added in the following months

Post requisites

1. Developed **models and simulations duly implemented in the graphical DT,**
2. Port decarbonization scenario to contribute **to RES increase** in the Port
3. Port decarbonization scenario to contribute **to decrease of CO2** in the Port,

Actors

Name	Type	Role
UTA	Human	Provide access to data
ENAPOR	System	Provide access to data
ELECTRA	System	Provide access to data
AUGMENTCITY DT	System	Provide the graphical DT

Scenario List

1. Increase in the share of renewables

In the first scenario, additional RES will be added to IMT's multi-scale models to simulate the impact on the port's decarbonisation and electrification plans. In this scenario, both planned PV installations by the Port and theoretical scenarios will be analysed.

2. Optimization models for ideal balancing

In this scenario, the best balancing options will be analysed taking into account multiple variables, such as: charging needs, consumption and generation profiles, weather forecast, demand-side flexibility schemes, among others. Different

scenarizations will be made to enhance port decarbonisation and maximise RES penetration and self-consumption.

Ålesund is an archipelago city with multiple embedded cruise ships, fishing vessels, and cargo terminals. Its 83'000 inhabitants are spread over 3 606 km². There is an urgent need to supply the ships with shore power, e.g., placing more RES in the grid in order to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and align with the Norwegian policies. Ålesund is not connected to the national transmission grid, thus it presents a closed and unique environment in the context of the energy value chain. It has a mix of the energy resources, however the most of them come from the hydropower installations.

UC1	Port Decarbonisation - Alesund
Description	
Short Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improve the operational efficiency of the island with regard to reducing greenhouse gas emissions and optimizing energy use with a focus on electricity demand and renewable energy sources, integrating advanced DT (AUGM) and AI technologies (IMT) - Test and validate the developed components in the defined scenarios
Objectives and Scope	
Objectives	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Collection and enrichment of data from stakeholders and involved parties. 2. Development of scenarios based on the data and challenges detailed on ORION Project. 3. Test and validate the developed components in WP3 (via IMT) and recommendations for sizing, timing throughout the day to optimize energy use with a focus on electricity 4. Provide recommendations for energy demand and renewable energy sources considering sustainability and flexibility over time.
Related Use Cases	UC1 is a two-headed UC, thus synergies and interactions between Cape Verde and Norway islands will be natural.
Related ORION Objectives [section 1.1.1]	- O3: Deliver data-driven decision system components to increase RES share with a focus on hydro energy in the local grid and reduce fossil fuels consumption in closed environments (ports);

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - O4: Advance AI-supported tools for operation and maintenance of large-scale solar energy plants to increase the energy availability and reliability (Task 3.4); - O5: Create, AUGMENTCITY AS develop and test the human-centric Digital Twin applications that are interoperable and implementable at different scales and use cases in order to provide the stakeholders with evidence-based information, support their decision making and enable best practise exchange globally (Task 3.5) 	
Related ORION Technical Solutions [section 1.1.2]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Human-centric Digital Twin applications (1.1.2.1) - Digital asset information components (1.1.2.4) 	
Pilot Sites	Alesund, Norway	
Stakeholders		
Name	Type	Role/Interest
SUAS	Primary	Link the Orion Project with Alesund stakeholders, gather data from local stakeholders, support the partners in testing, validating the developed solutions, and provide recommendations for energy demand and renewable energy sources, considering sustainability and flexibility over time.
AUGMENTCITY AS	Primary	Use case leader; Testing and Validation; Human-centric DT applications
IMT	Primary	Development of the AI and optimization algorithms that will optimise energy usage in order to reduce CO2 emissions
RWTH	Secondary	Cloud-based platform responsible for data harmonisation
Use Case Conditions		
Prerequisites	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Data availability (e.g. from SCADA systems) 2. Vessel name/engine characteristics (port information). 3. Power consumption at the shore station, and power consumption of EVs connected. 4. Weather (temperature, precipitation, irradiation). 5. Power generation data and water consumption data. 6. Other prerequisites may be added in the following months 	

Post requisites	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Developed models and simulations duly implemented in the graphical DT, 2. Port decarbonization scenario to contribute to RES increase in the Port 3. Port decarbonization scenario to contribute to decrease of CO2 in the Port, 	
Actors		
Name	Type	Role
SUAS	Human	Provide access to data
PLUG	System	Provide access to power data
ELHUB	System	Provide access to power data
AUGMENTCITY DT	System	Provide the graphical DT
Scenario List		
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Port decarbonisation In the first scenario, the goal is to find an optimal balance between port activities, energy demand and RES generation. In this scenario, the development of future what / if plans based on the port's data and challenges will be addressed. All these plans will be tested and recommendations to optimise energy usage and boost decarbonisation will be crafted. 2. Alesund city decarbonisation The second scenario expands all the what/if plans to the city level. As such, recommendations for energy demand and renewable energy sources for the port and the city development area, considering sustainability and flexibility over time (until 2030) will be rolled out using IMT's multi-scale models. 		

3.2. Use Case 2: Portugal

This Use Case approaches the operation and maintenance of large-scale PV installations.

EDP implemented Villacastin and Cruz del Hierro as hybrid farms, located in Spain, which combine solar and wind power. Cruz del Hierro is a PV farm located in Ávila, Spain, with 28.75 MW and Villacastin is a PV farm located in Segovia, Spain, with 28.2 MW, owned and operated by EDP Renewables (EDPR).

These farms face the typical challenges of a PV farm, which consists of: a) minimizing the operation and maintenance costs, leading to a lower LCOE, b)

being able to autonomously identify anomalies and faults, c) integrating predictive maintenance techniques, to anticipate potential failures and maximise the plant's availability, and d) using AI to support simple O&M decisions taking into account the market prices and market participation strategies.

UC2		Large PV Scale
Description		
Short Description	Enhance the operational efficiency of photovoltaic (PV) plants by integrating advanced Digital Twin (DT) technology and Artificial Intelligence (AI). The focus is on AI-driven simulations for near real-time monitoring and anomaly detection within key PV components. Additionally, it will implement predictive maintenance strategies, optimizing repair and maintenance scheduling based on economic factors like market dynamics and weather patterns.	
Objectives and Scope		
Objectives	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Improve Digital Twin to simulate and diagnose anomalies (EDP and INESC aim to improve DT / AI diagnosis tool that was developed in AI4PV project) 2. Improve fault classification model for elements of the PV plant (string inverters, transformer, PV panels) 3. Use AI to support the techno-economic decisions on when to perform repairing or maintenance activities, considering market prices' volatility and medium-term weather forecast 4. Test and validate the models in Villacastin and Cruz del Hierro PV farms 	
Related Use Cases	N.A.	
Related ORION Objectives [section 1.1.1]	O1, O2, O3	
Related ORION Technical Solutions [section 1.1.2]	Digital Asset Information Components (1.1.2.4)	
Pilot Sites	Villacastin and Cruz del Hierro	
Stakeholders		

Name	Type	Role/Interest
EDP	Leader	Use case leader; Developer of AI models; Infrastructure provider
INESC	Primary	Developer of AI fault classification models for PV plant components; Development of Modellica models to feed the Digital Twin
RWTH	Secondary	Cloud-based platform responsible for data harmonisation
AUGMENTCITY	Primary	AUGMENTCITY platform will be the graphical Digital Twin, thus representing all the implementations

Use Case Conditions

Prerequisites	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Data availability: SCADA, meteorological, etc 2. PV farms' CAD 3. PV farms' 3D model 4. Implementation of robust cybersecurity measures to safeguard the integrity and confidentiality of the analysed image data ensuring the reliability of the analysis system
----------------------	---

Post requisites	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Data integration with RWTH 2. Pre-visualisation of data in RWTH data collection hub 3. PV plants' visualisation in AUGMENTCITY platform 4. AI fault classification models and physical DT, developed and implemented by INESC, implemented in AUGMENTCITY platform
------------------------	--

Actors

Name	Type	Role
PV Plant Operator (EDP)	Human	Provide access to data
R&D Engineer (EDP)	Human	Steer the developments toward the needs of the end-user
INESC Modellica modules	System	Models representing the PV farms' electrical components
RWTH Platform	System	Cloud-based platform responsible for data harmonisation
AUGMENTCITY DT	System	Visualisation of PV farm operation in 3D environment

Scenario List

1. AI models (fault classification) of the PV modules

The AI models developed by INESC TEC will analyse all the processed and harmonised data from the PV farms and identify underperformances or anomalies

2. AI models (fault classification) of central inverters

The AI models developed by INESC TEC will analyse all the processed and harmonised data from the PV farms and identify underperformances or anomalies

3. AI models (fault classification) of PV farms remaining components (e.g. transformers)

The AI models developed by INESC TEC will analyse all the processed and harmonised data from the PV farms and and identify underperformances or anomalies

4. Other potential scenarios could be drafted and implemented

Additional scenarios will be analysed by EDP and INESC TEC, during the first year of the project. These potential scenarios will seek synergies with in-house developments and other ongoing projects (e.g. TALOS Horizon Europe project)

Scenario #1: AI models (fault classification) of the PV modules

Event	Process/activity description
1. Data Acquisition	PV farms' data is acquired from SCADA, meteorological stations, etc and transmitted to RWTH platforms
2. Algorithm Implementation	AI algorithms and deep learning models are employed in the data analysis module to perform an automated imagery analysis
	The analyzed data is stored in a database (RWTH)
3. Data Transmission	The analyzed data is ready to be sent and shared with AUGMENTCITY Digital Twin

Scenario #2: AI models (fault classification) of central inverters

Event	Process/activity description
1. Data Acquisition	PV farms' data is acquired from SCADA, meteorological stations, etc and transmitted to RWTH platforms
2. Algorithm Implementation	AI algorithms and deep learning models are employed in the data analysis module to perform an automated analysis of all the relevant data
	The analyzed data is stored in a database (RWTH)
3. Data Transmission	The analyzed data is ready to be sent and shared with AUGMENTCITY Digital Twin

Scenario #3: AI models (fault classification) of PV farms remaining components (e.g. transformers)

Event	Process/activity description
1. Data Acquisition	PV farms' data is acquired from SCADA, meteorological stations, etc and transmitted to RWTH platforms
2. Algorithm Implementation	AI algorithms and deep learning models are employed in the data analysis module to perform an automated analysis of all the relevant data to the specific asset (e.g. power transformers) The analyzed data is stored in a database (RWTH)
3. Data Transmission	The analyzed data is ready to be sent and shared with AUGMENTCITY Digital Twin

Information Exchanged

Name	Type	Description
SCADA data	Input	PV farms' operational data
Meteorological data	Input	Data coming from PV farms' meteorological stations
PV farms' CAD	Input	CAD to be used in RWTH and AUGMENTCITY platforms
Report/flags on faulty elements	Output	Information on the weather retrieved from the pilot site weather station (wind speed, wind direction, temperature, precipitation, humidity, etc.)

Additional Information

n.a.

3.3. Use Case 3: Slovenia

This Use Case approaches the operation and maintenance of floating offshore wave energy converters.

A prototype wave energy converter (WEC) device has been developed by Sigma Energy, Slovenia, and is currently deployed offshore of the coast of the city Bar in Montenegro. The WEC is a 30-kW grid-connected offshore wave power plant that is deployed at Sigma's own test site with a power and data cable connection with the shore. The device is a floating steel construction anchored to the ocean bottom, generating energy by using the up and down movement of ocean waves. The device is currently equipped with over 50 different sensors and sensor types plus 12 cameras.

SIGMA has developed its own software for monitoring and controlling the device that utilizes the device's sensor and camera information. This can be accessed from anywhere with via an internet connection and all data can be monitored in real-time as well as recorded for post-analysis purposes.

UC3		Wave Energy Converter – point absorber
Description		
Short Description	Operations and maintenance of floating offshore wave energy converters. LCOE cost reduction will contribute to the further deployment of this novel and promising green energy generator and will help to reduce EU energy dependence on imports of fossil fuels and reinforces its security of supply. Links to digital components are described in sections 1.1.2.1, 1.1.2.2.	
Objectives and Scope		
Objectives	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Develop novel sensor method for early fault detection based on acoustics/vibration data 2. Implement WEC in Digital Twin application 	
Related Use Cases	N.A.	
Related Objectives [section 1.1.1]	ORION	O1, O4, O5
Related Technical Solutions [section 1.1.2]	ORION	Human-centric Digital Twin applications (1.1.2.1) Sensor technologies (1.1.2.2)
Pilot Sites	Small scale test, if possible, towards the end of the project a large scale test in the ocean (no timeline yet)	
Stakeholders		
Name	Type	Role/Interest
SIGMA Energy	Leader	Use case leader; Developer of WEC; Infrastructure provider
SINTEF	Primary	Developer of structural health monitoring method based on vibration /acoustic data.
RWTH	Secondary	Basic data transfer (data stream, data storage (raw and analysed))
AUGMENTCITY	Secondary	Graphical representation of WEC in DT (Demo mode)
Use Case Conditions		

Prerequisites	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. NDA between SINTEF, SIGMA, RWTH and AUGM 2. Data availability: meteorological, ocean wave (height, period) etc 3. WEC CAD/3D model 4. WEC specs 5. Data available from previous tests used for development of sensor solution/method for condition monitoring 6.
Post requisites	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Method/measurement definition from SINTEF, output processed data and results for condition monitoring of the WEC transferred for visualization in the GDT (will be developed from available data and basin test) 2. Data flow: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Raw data from Sigma Energy to RWTH b. Data storage RWTH c. Raw data from Data storage (RWTH) to SINTEF d. Data Processing/Analysis of vibration data ((SINTEF) to monitor WEC condition e. Analysed data/results from SINTEF to RWTH (data storage) f. Raw data & analysed data from data storage (RWTH) to Augment CITY 3. WEC visualisation in AUGMENTCITY platform, with results/processed data

Actors

Name	Type	Role
Sigma Energy	System	Provide access to data, define needs, carry out tests
SINTEF Method	System	Method for early damage detection
RWTH Platform	System	Cloud-based platform responsible for data harmonisation
AUGMENTCITY DT	System	Visualisation of WEC operation in 3D environment

Scenario List

1. Basin test
Small scale tests in wave basin with downscaled WEC devices

2. 30 kW Data scenario

Developed methods will be tested on the data available from the previous test with a 30 kW WEC that was operational for ~6 month

3. Full test

Uncertain at the moment, but if another full-scale test will be carried out, test developed methods in a real scenario

Scenario #1: Basin Test

Event	Process/activity description
1. Test definition	SINTEF will carry out numerical modelling to define sensing set-up
2. Wave basin tests	Tests in the wave basin are carried out by Simga
3. Data collection	Data from the tests is collected by Sigma
4. Data Storage	The analyzed data is stored in a database provided by RWTH
5. Method development	Development of data analysis method using signal processing and ML algorithms

Scenario #2: 30 kW Data scenario

Event	Process/activity description
1. Data transmission	The analyzed data is ready to be sent and shared with SINTEF for method testing and AUGMENTCITY Digital Twin
2. Method testing and refining	Method testing developed in Scenario 1 on the 30 kW test data by SINTEF
3. Demo DT	Implementation of test site into a demo DT by AUGMENTCITY

Scenario #3: Full test

Event	Process/activity description
1. Sensor setup	Help defining the location and type of sensor and sensor setups
2. Data transmission	Real time (?) data transmission, RWTH
3. Method evaluation	Evaluation of developed methods by SINTEF
4. Demo DT	Implementation of test site into a demo DT

Information Exchanged

Name	Type	Description
Wave data	Input	Wave height and period data
Meteorological data	Input	Data coming from meteorological stations

WEC's CAD	Input	CAD to be used in RWTH and AUGMENTCITY platforms
Vibration data	Input	Vibration data collected on the WEC device
Report/flags on faulty elements	Output	Processed vibration data used to detect critical/changed parts
Additional Information		
n.a.		

3.4. Use Case 4: Brazil

This Use Case approach is the distributed co-simulation infrastructure connecting real-time simulation facilities in support of a Digital Twin.

Co-simulation is a mature technique and has been widely employed to integrate different domains in several fields of power systems analysis, e.g., transient stability analysis (TSA) and electromagnetic simulation (EMT). Within this context, the purpose of this case is to implement a geographically distributed co-simulation infrastructure connecting real-time simulation facilities located in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil. The goal is to develop a full digital twin of the transmission grid in the region as distributed implementation and contribute to the Digital Twin development.

UC4	GDS – Geographically Distributed co-Simulation
Description	
Short Description	<p>Co-simulation is a mature technique and has been widely employed to integrate different domains in several fields of power systems analysis, e.g., transient stability analysis (TSA) and electromagnetic simulation (EMT).</p> <p>The proposed test case is to integrate the LAFAE real-time simulator with the ONS (the Brazilian System Operator) real-time facility, in such a way that the studied renewable sources and its associated control systems are represented at the LAFAE side and the rest of the system, including replicas of the Brazilian HVDC links, are simulated at the ONS side, in a distributed hardware-in-the-loop approach.</p>
Objectives and Scope	
Objectives	1. Integrate different real-time simulators

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Ensure the simulation stability and accuracy, given the loss of data and latency that exist in the network connection between the simulators. 3. Develop interface models that compensate the latency and loss of data. 4. Integrate the data modelling approach developed within the project 	
Related Use Cases	N.A.	
Related ORION Objectives [section 1.1.1]	O5 ,O6	
Related ORION Technical Solutions [section 1.1.2]	Data and models interoperability components (1.1.2.3) Co-simulation between two stakeholders (1.2.2.4)	
Pilot Sites	Co-simulation with different real-time simulators, OPAL-RT, TYPHOON HIL and RTDS, that may employ different communication protocols	
Stakeholders		
Name	Type	Role/Interest
LAFEA (UFRJ)	Leader	Use case leader; Developer of GDS algorithms; Testing and Validation of Renewable Sources Integration to the Grid
ONS – Brazilian ISO	Primary	Testing and Validation of Brazilian Electrical System; Infrastructure provider
AUGM	Primary	Deploy graphical DT interface
Use Case Conditions		
Prerequisites	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Data availability: electrical parameters for each stakeholder to model its assets 2. Established secure internet communication protocols 	
Post requisites	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Methodology for Validating the Representativeness of Data Generated in GDS 2. Data integration with RWTH 	
Actors		
Name	Type	Role
LAFEA	System	Implement the Geographically Distributed Simulation (GDS) algorithms on each site;

		carry out tests on the integration of Renewable Energies to the electrical grid
ONS	System	Provide equivalent grid models based on real data from ISO;

Scenario List

1. Co-Simulation Validation Test

st to validate the GDS infrastructure implemented at both sites

2. Benchmark Test

lize the GDS infrastructure to simulate a benchmark test of integration of renewable energy into the Brazilian electrical grid, using the full potential from each stakeholder pertise

3. Additional tests

Without definition at the current moment, but more tests could be made to evaluate specific aspects of the electrical grid, such as Brazilians new HVDC link.

Scenario #1: Co-Simulation Validation Test

Event	Process/activity description
1.GDS Infrastructure Implementation	LAFAE and ONS are implementing the necessary steps for a secure connection to exchange data for the GDS
2. Test Definition	Define the test to validate the algorithms for GDS proper communication – i.e. the impact of latency and delays
3. Data collection	Data is collected and analysed to check if proper communication has been made
4. Adjustments	Based on the data, check if adjustments are required for the algorithms in order to implement the correct GDS

Scenario #2: Benchmark Test

Event	Process/activity description
1. Benchmark definition	The proper benchmark scenario is defined between the stakeholder to attend both interests with this methodology
2. Data Collection and Analysis	Data is collected and analyzed to assess the representativeness of the results, considering the level of detail employed in the models in comparison to local simulations.

Information Exchanged

Name	Type	Description
------	------	-------------

Equivalent Parameters	Grid	Input	Electrical parameters that define the equivalent grid connected to the renewable energy source
Meteorological data		Input	Data coming from meteorological stations to feed the LAFAE models of renewable energy sources
Additional Information			
n.a.			

3.5. Use Case 5: Canada

This Use Case approaches the modelling, monitoring, and reliable operations of energy generation and power electricity systems.

As the largest natural gas and oil producer in Canada, the Province of Alberta is committed to increasing the amount of green energy, including a legislated target of 30% renewable electricity by 2030. To achieve this goal, various energy conservation initiatives have been proposed in Alberta's energy sector, including renewable energy generation and EVs. Research activities have been conducted at ALBE to support such initiatives and create data-centric solutions for efficient and reliable integration of environment-friendly power generation and distribution.

UC5	Data-centric solutions for efficient and reliable power generation and distribution
Description	
Short Description	Data-centric solutions for efficient and reliable power generation and distribution
Long Description	Alberta, Canada's energy powerhouse, is pioneering green energy transitions, targeting 30% renewable electricity by 2030. Supported by Alberta's power sector, research at the Advanced Control and Diagnosis Lab (ACDL) and Energy Digitization Lab (ENTAIL) in the Faculty of Engineering at the University of Alberta focus on applying data-centric and AI-based techniques to industrial analytics, health monitoring, and system integration.
Objectives and Scope	

Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop methodologies to improve model accuracy when plant data is multi-modal, nonstationary, and subject to noises and disturbances. Various multi-variate statistical analysis and machine learning approaches, DNNs, and transfer learning techniques will be researched. • Design DT model for system and process health monitoring. • Fault detection and post-fault operations of power electronic systems. • Modelling of power grid impact of DER and EV integration. 	
Related Use Cases		
Related ORION Objectives [section 1.1.1]	O3, O5, O6 described in sections 1.1.2.1, 1.1.2.3, 1.1.2.4, 1.1.2.5.	
Related ORION Technical Solutions [section 1.1.2]	1.1.2.3 Data and models interoperability components 1.1.2.5 Data-driven decision systems components	
Pilot Sites		
Stakeholders		
Name	Type	Role/Interest
Univ. of Alberta (ALBE)	Leader	Developing methodologies, frameworks and algorithms, perform data collection, analysis, simulations and validations, connect to local industry stakeholders (e.g. members of Alberta Power Industry Consortium)
RWTH	Secondary	Developer of Cloud-based platform. Data management and integrator, develop API interfaces for different stakeholders. Embedding model methods into cloud-based platform.
AUGMENTCITY	Secondary	Developer of graphical digital twin models
Use Case Conditions		
Prerequisites	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Data collection/requisition, pre-processing 2. Technical solutions development 3. Validation using data 	

Post requisites	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Data integration with RWTH 2. Pre-visualisation of data in RWTH data collection hub 3. Visualisation of results in AUGM's DT
------------------------	---

Actors

Name	Type	Role
RWTH Platform	System	Cloud-based platform responsible for data harmonisation and model methods
ALBE Models/algorithms	System	Algorithms and models that are developed for energy industry anomaly detection and diagnostics
AUGMENTCITY	Systems	Help incorporate scenario cases in the graphical digital twin model

Scenario List

1. Fault classification model based on feature fusion applied to industrial facilities' electrical machines
2. Autonomous open-circuit switch fault detection, localization (FDL) and fault tolerant control (FTC) for modular multi-level converters (MMCs)
3. Voltage level and phase imbalance analysis at the DSO level

Scenario #1: Fault classification model based on feature fusion applied to industrial facilities' electrical machines

Event	Process/activity description
Data acquisition	Two Datasets acquired: one dataset from open-source platform and one data set collected from a testbed for rotor structural faults
Algorithm design and test	<p>A unique DL model is developed that achieves accurate fault classification through fusion of statistical features of time-series and DL model latent features</p> <p>Results have been prepared as a journal paper.</p>

Information Exchanged

Name	Type	Description
To be decided	Data	Data format needs to be determined

Additional Information

n.a.

Scenario #2	Autonomous open-circuit FDL and FTC for MMCs	
Event	Process/activity description	
Modeling	MMC modelling and normal performance analysis	
Algorithm design	A novel open-circuit switch fault detection and localization scheme is designed based on circulating current and switching frequency in MMCs. Once detected and isolated, the fault-induced effects can be compensated by a fault tolerant model predictive control.	
Experiment validation	The proposed scheme has been tested on a lab-scale MMC setup	
Information Exchanged		
Name	Type	Description
To be decided	data	Data formats need to be determined
Additional Information		
n.a.		
Scenario #3	Voltage level and phase imbalance analysis at DSO level	
Event	Process/activity description	
Modeling	Modelling of distribution grid and analysis of impact of DER and EV on voltage level and phase imbalance in power distribution systems.	
Algorithm design	Development of a machine learning-based approach for identifying voltage level and phase imbalance issues associated with the high penetration of distributed energy resources (DERs) and electric vehicles (EVs), and the design of energy management and coordination strategies to mitigate voltage issues and enhance the resilience of distribution systems.	
Experiment validation	Testing of developed algorithms on real or simulated (as available) distribution system data.	
Information Exchanged		
Name	Type	Description
To be decided	data	Data formats need to be determined
Additional Information		
n.a.		

4. State of the Art

4.1. Sensor Technologies

The offshore renewable energy sector continues to expand, driven by the necessity to transition from fossil fuels to green options. However, significant challenges persist in terms of operational environments, maintenance costs, and structural integrity monitoring. Offshore installations face extreme environmental conditions that lead to increased wear and tear of their structures. Robust and reliable construction and monitoring systems are critical for addressing these challenges. The development of large wind turbines with capacities ranging from 15 to 17 MW for increased energy production introduces new challenges [1].

Figure 2 - Regional onshore and offshore wind outlook for new installations (GW). GWEC's Global Wind Report 2023 features the latest key statistics of the status report for the global wind industry. [2]

The increased size and power output result in significantly larger forces acting on the turbine tower and foundation. Therefore, these forces must be managed carefully to ensure structural stability and operational reliability. Offshore wind parks, including floating structures, experience high operation and maintenance costs, contributing up to 25–30% of total lifecycle costs [3].

Even though wind turbines are still the most important method of offshore energy production, new methods using ocean waves to generate energy are being studied [1]. Wave energy converters (WECs) with floats (point-type absorbers), while fundamentally different in their ways of generating energy, share several common construction features with offshore floating wind farms. These shared features include structural elements designed to withstand harsh marine environments and the use of advanced anchoring systems to ensure stability in dynamic ocean conditions. This similarity facilitates the transfer of knowledge and technology between these renewable energy sectors, contributing to the optimization of construction methods and the development of more robust systems for offshore applications.

Figure 3 - Floating offshore wind turbines. The WindFloat Atlantic project, the first Offshore Wind Farm in Portugal installed on floating platforms. [4]

Figure 4 - Wave Energy Converter. AWS Ocean Energy, 16 kW Archimedes Waveswing wave energy converter. [5]

The harsh and dynamic marine environments faced by wave energy converters (WECs) and other offshore systems make it challenging but necessary to ensure that the operations and generation of energy are reliable during long periods of time. Offshore facilities face significant challenges during major storms. These structures become practically inaccessible, making real-time monitoring and predictive fault detection crucial for their reliability and longevity. Implementing advanced predictive systems not only enhances operational efficiency but also enables proactive measures to mitigate potential damage. Advanced State-of-Health (SOH) monitoring systems can also help to address these challenges through remote monitoring, allowing operators to monitor the structural integrity of offshore constructions and anchoring in real time. By enabling condition-based maintenance through early damage detection, these systems facilitate timely and cost-effective repairs, significantly reducing both overall downtime and maintenance costs.

In wind turbine condition monitoring, the primary focus is on the moving components within the Nacelle, like the rotor, gearbox and bearing system [15,16]. Condition monitoring measurements on land-based wind turbine towers and blades have been carried out [17]. However, non-destructive inspections of these parts are still the standard. Vibration monitoring can be categorized into two main approaches within modal analysis: measuring vibration patterns and acoustic emission measurements.

Acoustic emission measurements rely on acoustic or vibration sensors triggered by high-energy event signals generated by subtle defects, such as small cracks or stiffness reductions [6]. These signals are normally high-frequency signals that are damped quickly. This technique is used successfully in the nacelle to

monitor possible damage to the bearing system and the gearbox. However, applying this technique to large structural parts such as the tower or wings of wind turbines presents challenges due to the required large number of devices and the associated higher costs and complexity. Nevertheless, it has been applied to monitor towers and wings[18]. The data obtained by acoustic emission monitoring enables early-stage detection of potential faults, allowing for timely interventions to prevent more severe damage and reduce repair costs and operational downtime

Alternatively, modal analysis using vibration sensors, such as displacement sensors, velocity sensors, and accelerometers, can be used to monitor the vibrations of small and large structures. Usually, measurements from multiple sensors are combined to analyse the vibration patterns of the structure connected to the structure's eigenfrequencies. This is a particularly effective method to detect dynamic changes that indicate signs of degradation like material fatigue, misalignment, or potential damage to, e.g., mooring lines and foundations by detecting changes in the vibration pattern (vibration modes) over time. This early detection of degradation enables precise interventions before the problems escalate.

Related here is also the measurement of strain which has become of larger interest in recent years due to the use of fibre cables for Distributed Strain Sensing and Distributed Acoustic Sensing [19]. Here, the fibre cable acts as a large number of discrete sensors, allowing many measurement points along large structures.

Experiments to monitor the blades have been carried out by analysing acoustic emission signals in the Tower and blades [20].

Monitoring the structural integrity of offshore systems [19] relies heavily on advanced monitoring systems due to their inaccessibility and the continuous stress exerted on the structure by waves, currents, and wind. [6]. A critical part of floating offshore structures, whether wind or WEC, is the fastening to the ocean floor with mooring lines. Due to the harsh conditions and large forces acting on these mooring lines, they are prone to failure, which can lead to catastrophic failure of the structure as the mooring lines ensure the fastening and stability of the entire construction. Recent studies have started investigating the possibility of using vibration measurement and AI-based analyses for early damage detection [21,22].

The integration of both types of sensors with advanced digital tools and remote data acquisition systems enhances its effectiveness. These technologies allow operators to monitor structural performance in real-time, even in remote offshore locations, facilitating condition-based maintenance strategies [6].

For floating structures like WECs and offshore wind turbines, where the anchoring systems are vital to maintaining stability, it is particularly important to ensure the integrity of mooring lines and prevent failures that could compromise energy production or safety [6].

Recent advances in Model Predictive Control (MPC) highlight its ability to optimize energy capture in Wave Energy Converters (WECs), particularly in dynamic offshore environments. MPC efficiently handles multiple models, objectives, and system constraints, making it essential for maximizing energy capture and reducing the Levelized Cost of Energy (LCoE). A critical aspect of these systems is the integration of advanced sensors to estimate and predict Wave Excitation Force (WEF) in real-time, eliminating the need for external wave observation systems, simplifying implementation and reducing operational costs [7]. This approach ensures greater adaptability to the dynamic conditions of the marine environment while promoting operational stability by adjusting control parameters in real time [7]. Although promising, MPC faces significant challenges related to model accuracy and system robustness. Studies have revealed that errors in parameters such as mass and stiffness can lead to concerning phenomena, such as instability and lock-up, compromising efficiency [7]. To mitigate these problems, the use of robust WEF predictors, combined with adjustments to the linear damping coefficient, has proven effective [7]. Here, the integration of sensors and adaptive control algorithms can compensate for non-linear forces, such as static and viscous friction, optimizing energy capture and reducing operational risks [7].

Built-in Wave Energy Converters (BI-WECs) bring innovations that enhance the reliability and efficiency of wave energy conversion systems. These devices encapsulate internal components within floating structures, such as buoys and horizontal cylinders, shielding them from direct impacts, saltwater corrosion, and biofouling — factors that commonly affect the longevity of offshore systems [8]. The modularity of BI-WECs allows their application in various maritime equipment, ranging from signalling buoys to unmanned vehicles, reducing maintenance requirements in long-term operations [8]. The hydrodynamic response of these devices, however, remains a critical focus for improving energy capture efficiency.

Additionally, hybrid PTO (Power Take-Off) systems, combining triboelectric and electromagnetic technologies, have been developed to enhance energy conversion efficiency under variable conditions [8].

The implementation of the Hardware-In-The-Loop (HIL) methodology has proven essential in advancing renewable energy systems, particularly in offshore environments. By combining actual and simulated components, HIL enables precise testing of wave energy converters (WECs) and power take-

offs (PTOs) under extreme marine conditions, reducing costs and improving efficiency. This approach supports the early detection of faults in system components, enhances real-time control capabilities, and accelerates the research-to-market process by addressing operational challenges during the design phase. Moreover, HIL facilitates the integration of advanced sensors, such as vibration and acoustic emission sensors, which are crucial for monitoring structural integrity and optimizing energy capture in dynamic ocean environments. These capabilities underline the critical role of HIL in creating resilient, efficient, and adaptive renewable energy technologies for harsh offshore conditions [9]

(a)

(b)

Figure 5 - Hardware-in-the-loop simulation of wave energy converters and power take-offs. Hardware-in-the-loop simulation methods for wave energy converters propose a classification framework based on simulated, real, and interface subsystems to improve organization and application. [9]

Advanced control strategies, such as those evaluated in a HIL framework, highlight the dependence on real-time feedback from sensors to monitor critical parameters like excitation force and displacement. A significant challenge arises when sensor data is compromised due to faults or loss of functionality, which can severely impact energy capture efficiency and system stability. To address these challenges, Bayesian reinforcement learning has been proposed by the researchers of IEEE as a fault recovery method, enabling adaptive control systems to compensate for sensor loss and continue operation under model mismatch conditions [10]. This fault-tolerant approach underscores the necessity of robust sensor integration for achieving reliable WEC operation across varying sea states [10].

Sensor technologies also face limitations regarding noise interference and environmental wear, particularly when monitoring mechanical components like gearboxes. In such scenarios, vibration sensors are critical for fault diagnosis, capturing detailed data on issues such as gear pitting or tooth breakage. However, the accuracy of these sensors is often hindered by noise and harsh offshore conditions. To overcome these limitations, recent work has combined convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and long short-term memory (LSTM) algorithms, optimized with Adam¹, to filter noise and improve fault detection accuracy [11]. These machine learning-enhanced diagnostic systems demonstrate a growing trend toward integrating advanced computational models with sensor technologies to enhance fault detection capabilities. While such approaches are promising for gearbox-specific monitoring, their applicability may be restricted in broader WEC systems without significant computational resources or stable connectivity for real-time analysis [11].

The convergence of fault-tolerant controls and machine learning-based diagnostics highlights the critical role of sensors as enablers of adaptive and intelligent WEC systems. Fault recovery mechanisms like Bayesian reinforcement learning offer resilience to data loss, making them suitable for standalone WECs operating in remote locations with limited maintenance access [10]. Meanwhile, vibration sensor-based diagnostics, supported by deep learning, are particularly effective for ensuring the longevity of mechanical subsystems like gearboxes, which are prone to degradation under high operational loads [11].

The I.nano.WEC project developed by the civil engineering department of the Faculty of Engineering at the University of Porto introduces an innovative approach by integrating triboelectric nanogenerators (TENGs) into maritime

¹ Adam is an optimization algorithm that can be used instead of the classical stochastic gradient descent procedure to update network weights iterative based in training data.

buoys, which, in addition to offering energy efficiency of up to 500 W/m²[12], open new possibilities for supporting sensor systems in offshore environments. Through advanced nanofabrication techniques, TENGs are optimized to operate under harsh marine conditions, such as high salinity and biofouling, enhancing their durability and making them suitable for powering sensors designed for environmental monitoring, aquaculture systems, and maritime signalling [12]. This technology improves the robustness of offshore systems and enables the operational feasibility of sensors in remote locations, providing stable energy for continuous monitoring of environmental and structural variables.

Figure 6 - Triboelectric Nanogenerators: devices that generate energy through waves. Researchers from IFIMUP, FEUP, and INEGI (Portugal) have developed three triboelectric nanogenerators that generate electricity from the movement of waves. The goal is to install them on ocean buoys to increase the operation time without human intervention. [13]

Integrating Wave Energy Converters (WECs) into port infrastructure, such as breakwaters, highlights the critical role of pressure sensors and structural monitoring systems in assessing performance and durability. One significant challenge in these setups is the complex interaction between hydrodynamic forces and structural elements, which requires accurate real-time data to ensure stability and energy efficiency. Pressure sensors play a pivotal role in capturing these forces, providing data essential for evaluating wave impacts and optimizing the performance of hybrid systems like oscillating water column (OWC) WECs integrated into port breakwaters [14]. A key proposal involves coupling these sensors with advanced data acquisition systems to enhance the precision of hydrodynamic modelling, allowing for more robust designs that can withstand varying wave conditions [14].

Despite their potential, pressure sensors in such environments face restrictions, mainly related to sensor durability under prolonged exposure to marine conditions, including biofouling and corrosion. Solutions to these issues include using protective coatings and regular calibration to maintain accuracy over time [14]. This trend of integrating WECs into multi-functional port structures maximizes the utility of existing infrastructure and enables cost-sharing between energy production and coastal protection, making it particularly suitable for regions with high wave activity and significant maritime traffic [14]. As WEC technology advances, the role of structural monitoring systems in hybrid infrastructures is expected to grow, driving the development of more resilient, efficient, and versatile energy systems for the blue economy.

4.2. Data and model interoperability components

In the modern age of science and technology, the need for efficient and standardized data exchange is growing between Transmission System Operators (TSOs) and Distribution System Operators (DSOs). The role of IEC standards is critically important, especially the CIM and its Common Grid Model Exchange Standard (CGMES), in supporting TSO-DSO coordination. Several European projects such as OneNet, EU-SysFlex, INTERFACE, and TDX-ASSIST have laid the foundation for data exchange and interoperability by highlighting gaps and analyzing data exchange requirements. Bytyqi et al. [23] highlight the need to open access to the CIM Unified Modelling Language (UML) model to encourage contributions to model extensions. The findings align with broader TSO-DSO interoperability efforts, including initiatives like the European Commission's Smart Grids Task Force (SGTF), BRIDGE Data Management Working Group, and IEC TC57 WG13 activities.

Currently, the IEC has a series of standards for CIM. Some of these standards are described as follows [24]:

- IEC 61970: The main objective of this series is to produce standards in the power transmission segment dealing with the Energy Management System (EMS) applications. It promotes interoperability between EMS systems or applications developed by different vendors.
- IEC 61968: The key objective of this series is to produce standards facilitating inter-application integration of various distributed software application systems that support the management of utility electrical distribution networks.
- IEC 62325: This series aims to produce standards for the electricity market segment. It promotes interoperability between electricity market application software developed independently by different vendors.

Balijepalli et al. [24] highlight key challenges in improving CIM to facilitate the emerging concept of power system DTs. CIM provides a unified vocabulary for

communication between various power system applications following IEC-defined already established open standards. The emergence of DTs, presenting a real-time cyber-physical representation of power systems, pushes CIM to evolve to meet technological advancements. The detailed analysis of CIM's application from power generation to distribution, electricity markets, and consumer interactions stresses its key role in the interoperability of smart grids and DTs. The research has also highlighted gaps in integrating CIM with BIM and proposed a system-level use case to handle the deficiencies.

Zhijun et al. [25] underscore the limitations of the CIM in addressing challenges to modern power systems related to the adoption of power of the IoT and DT technologies. Authors have proposed improvements and extensions to the CIM framework based on IEC 61970/968 standards. The key focus areas include power system resources and equipment assets, station geographical region modelling, equipment component modelling, and measurement types. The relationships between geographical area and equipment, equipment and components, components and measurement have also been made. Not only theoretically but also, the proposed model has been implemented practically in substation projects. Advanced functionalities like integration of video Imaging, 3D simulation, and fusion display of multidimensional measurement data for conducting equipment support applications like remote monitoring, auxiliary analysis, and decision-making. Additionally, the importance of separating equipment and measurement models within the CIM framework has also been presented to fulfil modern applications' demands. The feasibility of these improvements, assistance in integrating video imaging, spatial area modelling, and equipment/component status monitoring have also been validated with the substation digital projects. The improved CIM framework is compatible with modern applications like analysis of equipment conditions and trend prediction. Future courses of action have also been suggested to benefit from CIM's potential in advanced digital systems, such as 3D digital asset management, application algorithms, and software configuration parameters.

Fan et al. [26] emphasize the crucial role of standardized models in improving the integration of RES into power grids through Information Technology (IT). Leveraging the IEC 62325 Environmental Package, the authors propose an application architecture integrating social data into renewable energy accommodation systems. The collected social data has been standardized and applied practically to the Jibei power grid, reflecting CIM extension based on the data-address-phenomenon-measurement-alert-event pattern. This improved information model demonstrates the capability of effectively unifying and managing renewable energy consumption data and fostering its adoption in renewable energy-dense provinces within the "Three Norths"

region of China while addressing the challenges of variability and demand. Integrating social data into the CIM framework under IEC 62325 has considerably improved forecasting accuracy, operational efficiency, and grid stability while increasing the grid's ability to accommodate RES. Achieving socio-environmental benefits, this integration supports the scalability of renewable energy technologies.

The future framework can focus on its extension to predictive algorithms for demand and response management, refining real-time data synchronization techniques, and developing scalable cloud-based solutions for broader regional and international applications. AI-driven analytics can also play a vital role in ensuring adaptability in increasing dynamic RES.

Cooke et al. [27] highlight the complications of traditional means in automating and synchronizing Power Quality (PQ) activities across utility systems. Traditional methods to maintain synchronization in protection engineering, billing, and operations require huge resources, especially for PQ teams that span multiple utility functions. To streamline these processes, authors have proposed CIM as an international standard by enabling the exchange of standard data and the creation of interoperable interfaces between utility applications. A roadmap to improve the current CIM framework has been presented while highlighting gaps within the existing PQ quantities represented within the CIM.

CIM plays a vital role in integrating modern applications as it enables interchanging data between utility applications, either within single or different utilities, in a cost-effective and standard manner. Existing work developed in the CIM can be utilized as a foundation for improvements required by PQ use cases.

Leveraging the CIM as a foundation, Wang et al. [28] present an approach for real-time monitoring and fault detection for overhead lines by developing a tree-structured data model. Without reducing database performance, CIM-XML files have been analyzed to develop rational tables accurately representing the complex relationships within the CIM. This Intelligent Monitoring System (IMS) supports scalability and adaptability for several application scenarios. With relative errors of 3.37% – 5.70%, the system responds in precise detection of voltage values from normal to critical stages. The response, in terms of accuracy and efficiency, is much better than the conventional high-voltage detection technologies. The CIM-based system has also reduced risk losses besides offering a theoretical foundation for pantograph design improvements by optimizing the dynamic performance of pantograph-overhead line interactions. Still, certain challenges have been faced in achieving real-time data processing and system stability under huge

data loads. Therefore, standardized, open architecture is required to enhance system integration and compatibility.

Existing power systems often lack the facility of a standardized framework for storing and sharing network data components, resulting in reduced efficiency and interoperability issues. These challenges have been addressed by Barros et al. [29] by leveraging the CIM for distribution based on IEC 61970-301 and IEC 61968-11 standards for unified representation of electrical components in distribution systems. Electrical components classes have been defined by generating CIM-compliant files using Enterprise Architect® software. It is then processed using Altova XMLSpy® to create a rational database schema. All important components of distribution networks, enabling seamless data storage and retrieval, have been organized in tabular format. This standardized data architecture, accessed by CIM RDF files, ensures interoperability and supports the transition of smart grid technologies. These RDF files closely match the reference standards, and the results highlight the effectiveness of the methodology. Future framework includes integration of more sophisticated SQL commands within stored procedures to improve database functionality and further automate CIM RDF file generation, resulting in efficient exchange of data in distribution networks.

Zomerdijk et al. [30] highlight that increasing interdependent communication and energy infrastructures are reshaping power systems where the role of DTs is vital in reforming physical as well as digital domains of the energy sector. The authors have proposed a vision for a standardized DT ecosystem architecture which can be integrated with the existing transmission and distribution system operations. The advanced concepts of microgrids and local energy communities can also be accommodated through a system-of-system approach. The architecture emphasizes bidirectional real-time data exchange, standardization of data, self-adaptive simulation models, and improved modular integration to handle planning and operational phases, including long-term infrastructure development. The main problems with such types of architectures include; model errors, managing measurement, uncertainty propagation, and the complications of aligning multi-DT systems. Authors have proposed an ecosystem architecture to address these challenges by connecting operation and planning modules to ensure high-fidelity simulations, tracking of error propagation, and robust scenario analysis. In this situation, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML), along with deep learning techniques such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks, play a crucial role in analyzing electrical signals and detecting anomalies. They are key enablers in overcoming major challenges, including large-scale data processing, fast and accurate system modeling, and enhancing predictive analysis. Transitioning

DTs from conceptual frameworks into successful practical reality in power systems is the need of the hour to increase collaboration between system operators and software developers for the establishment of standardized workflows, data-sharing protocols, and designing of the ecosystem.

CIM is flexible and efficient in integrating power system data and establishing a strong basis for interoperability, real-time monitoring, and effective data sharing. CIM plays a crucial role in advancing the integration of emerging technologies like DTs, RES, and IMS, facilitating more intelligent and resilient power grids. Extensions to CIM are still required to deal with more complex and advanced energy systems like enhanced 3D visualization, integration with BIM, and standardized workflow improvements are necessary for dynamic system modelling. For improved versions of the digital transformation of power systems, future courses of action need to focus on open-access frameworks, collaborative ecosystem designs, and leveraging AI and ML to address scalability, data synchronization, and predictive analytics challenges.

AI-driven fault detection, integrated with CIM-based digital twins, enhances power system stability by predicting failures in high-voltage networks, transformers, and renewable energy systems. Early detection and precise classification of faults can prevent catastrophic failures, minimize production losses, and optimize maintenance schedules [33]. For instance, in the context of power systems, timely identification of electrical faults can prevent widespread blackouts and ensure the stability of the grid [34]. Similarly, in oil and gas industries, accurate fault classification enables predictive maintenance strategies, reducing unplanned downtime and extending the lifespan of critical equipment. Recent developments in CNNs and LSTM networks, have shown remarkable success in extracting complex patterns from time series data, leading to more accurate fault classifications. These methods are particularly adept at handling the high-dimensional, noisy data often encountered in real-world industrial applications. Shao et al. [35] employed a DL model to automate the process of extracting features from motor current and vibrational data. In addition, their analysis was conducted in the Time-Frequency Domain (TFD) and used a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) to effectively extract features from the image maps created for both input signals (current and vibrational signals). In comparison to other conventional classifiers, their proposed method achieved an exceptional prediction accuracy of 99.87%. Similarly, Song et al. [36] combined Bayesian optimization with a residual CNN to classify ISCFs. Their work attained a classification accuracy of 97.83%. While individual deep learning models have shown remarkable success in time series fault classification, recent research has

increasingly focused on leveraging the power of ensemble learning techniques in combination with deep neural networks.

Ensemble learning methods, such as bagging and boosting, have been employed to further improve time-series fault classification performance by combining multiple models to reduce variance and bias. These methods enhance prediction accuracy and robustness, especially in noisy environments [37]. Stacking, or stacked generalization, is a more advanced ensemble method that employs a metalearning algorithm to determine the best way to combine predictions from multiple base models. This approach involves using diverse ensemble members and assessing their performance on out-of-sample data. A meta-model, or meta-learner, is then trained to synthesize these predictions, leveraging the strengths of different models to improve adaptability to complex and dynamic data patterns [38]. Recently, a thorough classification methodology based on a meta-learner stacking framework approach is proposed to detect inter-turn short circuit fault (ISCF) of a permanent magnet synchronous motor (PMSM), which is one of the common types of stator winding failures. Early detection of ISCFs can be challenging and if not identified during normal operation other faults such as phase-to-phase and phase-to-ground can rapidly escalate. The proposed method begins by transforming the unprocessed custom vibrational signal-based dataset into a segmented dataset. The dataset with windows is inputted into Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks to make predictions of class labels by exploiting the sequential learning capabilities of the LSTM model. At the same time, statistical feature extraction is conducted on the windowed dataset, leading to a dataset that has been extracted of its features. This feature dataset is used as input for two distinct base classifiers: a 1D Convolutional Neural Network (1DCNN) and the Random Forest (RF) algorithm. The 1DCNN focuses on local information within the dataset, whereas the Random Forest algorithm uses an ensemble approach to make robust classification. Gradient Boosting Classifier is used as a meta-learner. The meta-learner utilizes the predicted class label probabilities from three base classifiers (LSTM, 1DCNN, and RF) to generate the ultimate true label for the class.

For ML and AI to be deployed successfully in equipment health monitoring and fault detection and classification, identification of relevant features is extremely important. It becomes clearer that utilization of solely basic statistical features among data does not yield a high level of accuracy in fault classification. On the other hand, the exclusive dependence on machine learning-based feature extraction, without the incorporation of prior

knowledge, compromise the ability of the model to generalize. On top of that, poor quality regarding training data can also potentially affect the robustness of the model. To address such challenge, a unified feature fusion methodology is proposed recently [39], wherein the utilization of basic SFs is combined with the capability of Deep Learning (DL) model to facilitate comprehensive deep latent feature extraction to improve the fault classification accuracy. A modified DL architecture based on the second-generation wavelet decomposition theory is designed to effectively extract Adaptive Latent Features (ALFs) from rotational time series signals for the purpose of classifying Structural Rotor Faults (SRF).

A hybrid DL method is proposed that exploit the strengths of automated feature extraction capability of the DL models and the detailed signal characteristics captured by traditional Statistical Features (SFs), providing a more comprehensive diagnostic framework. For ALFs extraction the LN framework proposed by Pan et al., in [40] is modified by adding a residual layer after the update layer to avoid gradient vanishing and smoother feature learning. It has been established that the initial layers of CNN learn spectral features and these features get diminished as the network depth increases [41]. To avoid this, a skip connection/residual layer is added to allow the smooth flow of initial spectral information through this connection and also improves the robustness of the generated ALFs. For SFs, only the combination of frequency and time-domain features are used. This is because the DL network used to extract ALFs is based on second generation wavelet decomposition, so the extracted features will have time-frequency characteristics. Therefore, the final feature vector will have TD, TFD, and FD characteristics. Lastly, the Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LightGBM) is applied to the final feature vector to render the final classification instead of the softmax layer of the original LN. LightGBM is preferred due to its advantages, including histogram-based vertical learning instead of level-wise learning, which accelerates training by grouping continuous feature values into discrete bins, as well as GPU acceleration.

Another mechanism regarding the data and model interoperability is the Geographically Distributed Real-Time Digital Co-Simulation (GD-RTDCS) [31]. Deeply connected to the context of modern electrification of the world and the increase in distributed energy resources (DERs) participation in bulk power systems, new challenges regarding the operation and control of electrical systems emerge. The main challenges within the context of DERs integration are the need for multidomain and large-scale simulation and testing, and the

rapid changes in topology and synergies require constant testing and evaluation [31]. This rapid transformation calls for faster, more practical and, within the world of digitalization, global solutions that preserve data sensitivity and integrity. The GD-RTDCS meets these criteria and is expected to play a pivotal role in the energy transition [32], integrating multiple facilities into the same solution, utilizing each to their expertise and validating the synergy between multiple agents.

Finally, research has been done for fault detection and post-fault operations of power electronics. In recent years, multilevel converters (MMCs) have garnered significant interest in high and medium-voltage applications owing to their modular structure, easy scalability, superior output characteristics, and reduced switching losses. The utility of MMCs extends to many applications including motor drives, high-voltage DC power transmission systems, power transformers, and energy storage systems. The presence of many submodules (SMs) in MMCs guarantees high modularity, simple scalability, reduced switching frequency, and superior harmonic performance. On the other hand, reliability is a major issue due to the increased likelihood of switch faults caused by the high number of SMs. Semiconductor faults constitute more than 38% of power conversion failures and the absence of effective fault diagnosis and fault-tolerant mechanisms can lead to damage to other components and system malfunctions. Therefore, fault detection and localization (FDL) and fault tolerant (FT) techniques have emerged as effective strategies for enhancing the reliability of power converters, particularly for MMCs with large numbers of SMs. There has been extensive research work on open-circuit faults. Such a fault can go unnoticed for extended periods without triggering immediate system shutdowns. This leads to output waveform distortion with the potential to cause secondary faults. Hence, prompt identification and isolation of open circuit faults in MMCs is essential for smooth and continued operation.

In [42] a least-squares signal-based FDL technique implemented on only the highest and lowest capacitor voltages is employed to identify faulty SMs in MMCs. Such a method assumes that when a SM experiences an open-circuit fault, its capacitor voltage rises relative to the healthy SMs. However, this phenomenon depends on the modulation technique used, for example, when nearest level modulation (NLM), one of the most common modulation techniques, is used, the detection can become difficult under certain switch faults. Similarly, control algorithms that employ a voltage balancing technique will cause the same issue.

Once the faulty SM is localized, a FT strategy should be implemented to maintain the smooth and continuous functioning of the MMC. Various control strategies utilizing neutral shift have been implemented to enhance the maximum achievable line-to-line voltages of the MMC [43], [44]. These studies are focused on improving the control performance during post-fault conditions of MMCs.

4.3. Digital asset information components

The adoption of AI solutions has been rapidly growing, with increasing studies and applications across various industries, particularly in the renewable energy sector [45]. The ability of AI to develop innovative solutions to traditional problems has drawn significant attention from both academic researchers and industry professionals. Although data for renewable energy systems are often already collected, stored and displayed through systems such as SCADA, they are not always processed efficiently to extract meaningful insights that could enhance operational efficiency and effectiveness. AI offers tremendous potential to transform how renewable energy systems are designed, controlled, and maintained. By enabling the collection and analysis of vast amounts of data, AI can provide valuable insights into system performance to reach optimal efficiency. This approach is especially useful for O&M teams, who can leverage AI to monitor performance, detect faults early, predict future problems, and reduce system downtime.

The use of AI combined with DTs can further enhance data analysis, allowing more accurate monitoring and decision-making. For instance, if any deviations are detected when comparing real data with the data predicted by the DT, it may indicate a fault (fault in PV strings, wind turbine inverters, etc.). Another significant benefit of DTs is in testing future scenarios, where changes to system components can be evaluated to predict their impact on production, reliability, and overall system performance.

One of the most significant advances in AI applications for renewable energy is the detection of faults in PV systems, specifically in PVPPs. Faults in PV systems can be identified using ML techniques, which rely on two primary approaches. The first one is based on electrical signal processing, which uses electrical measurements from the PVPP devices, while the second one is based on image processing. The work of [46] encompasses these two methodologies, focusing on detecting and diagnosing faults in PV systems utilizing thermal imaging and inverter data. By using drone-based thermal imaging technology, the study is able to identify hotspot faults and bypass diode failures, two common issues that significantly degrade the performance of PV panels. These

faults are detected through image processing techniques, where the thermal images are analyzed for anomalies in the temperature distribution across the panels. Specifically, for thermal image analysis, the study uses Detectron2, a powerful computer vision model which employs Faster R-CNN, allowing the model to identify and classify faulty panels by analyzing the heat patterns. The thermal imaging is complemented by real-time inverter data, such as voltage and current measurements, which are processed using ML algorithms, including NNs, RFs, KNNs and GB. However, several challenges are encountered in implementing this technology. The primary issues include poor-quality thermal images caused by irregularities such as partial visibility of panel edges, shadows from surrounding objects, and variations in flight altitude. These factors complicate the task of detecting and categorizing faults. Moreover, the large volume of images and real-time data collected can lead to long processing times, which impacts the efficiency of the fault detection system. The study addresses these issues by improving the algorithm's performance to focus solely on thermal images, avoiding the complications introduced by RGB images, and reducing the dataset size for more efficient processing. By integrating visual inspection methods with ML models, the fault detection process becomes more automated and efficient, reducing the need for manual inspection of human operators and improving overall system maintenance and efficiency. The case study of [47] within the European project AI4PV focuses on using advanced technologies to improve the operational performance, reliability, and efficiency of PV systems. One of the primary goals of this study is to develop and validate models for early fault detection and classification by combining DT technology, AI and data analysis solutions. To address the challenges posed by faults, which can lead to performance degradation or complete system failures if not addressed promptly, this project uses a hybrid dataset combining real-world data from the real PVPP and synthetic data generated by a DT. This procedure simulates both normal and faulty conditions, which may not yet have occurred in the actual infrastructure, thus improving the model's robustness and capability to handle real-world faults. The study uses SCADA data, including currents, voltages, etc., and weather data, like irradiance and temperature, as inputs to ML models such as Decision Trees, RFs, KNNs, and ANNs. While the technology offers promising solutions, there are several challenges and limitations. One issue is the imbalance in the dataset between fault-free and faulty conditions, which can lead to overfitting in ML models. Furthermore, since the synthetic data generated by the DT may not perfectly reflect all possible fault scenarios, there is a risk that the models might not generalize well to unforeseen ones. The work of [48] within the DAPPER project no. HBC.2020.2144 proposes two ML models designed to enhance fault detection in PV systems: a RNN using GRUs and a GNN. To detect faults and estimate

power loss severity, the RNN model processes time-series data from a single PV site, including inverter current, voltage, and satellite-based weather data. The GNN model monitors multiple PV systems by comparing voltage and current measurements, eliminating the need for additional weather sensors. However, the models face several challenges, such as data imbalance, where common faults dominate the training data, and accuracy issues due to the inaccuracy of satellite-based weather data compared to local measurements, which can misclassify faults. To address these challenges, the authors introduced a penalized loss function to handle data imbalance and incorporated edge features in the GNN model, such as geographic distance and system configuration, to improve generalization to unseen sites.

For O&M solutions, AI techniques are used not only to detect faults but also to locate them. When it comes to fault location, several approaches are being explored using AI methods. The work in [49] proposes an effective method for detecting and locating faults in large-scale PV arrays. It focuses on using the CUSUM of the change in string currents to detect, identify and locate various faults, including low mismatch L-L, high resistance L-G faults and open circuit faults, even in challenging conditions such as low irradiance and partial shading. By analyzing the transient changes in current magnitudes, the method offers an accurate fault detection and location solution for PV system fault management. However, this method also faces several challenges. The first is the detection of faults that produce small changes in current, such as high resistance faults. Another challenge is the presence of non-fault scenarios, such as partial shading, which can cause changes in current magnitudes similar to faults. To address these, the proposed method uses a threshold comparison to distinguish between faults and non-fault conditions, ensuring accurate fault identification even during transient changes caused by environmental factors like moving clouds. The European project TALOS, under Grant Agreement no. 101119744, leverages AI for fault location and recommendation systems to improve the availability, reliability, and performance of PV systems and reduce operating and maintenance costs. This project faces some challenges, including the lack of faulty data, real-time data processing, and integration of AI with the existing infrastructures, which requires ensuring data integrity and managing the computational load for real-time operation. Also, the complex and various environmental conditions play a significant role since they can lead to greater confusion in the AI models. These challenges are addressed by using ML algorithms and analytics combined with DT technology to simulate fault scenarios and predict maintenance needs. By leveraging SCADA and weather data, TALOS reduces the need for costly sensors while enhancing system performance and safety. It also seeks to automate O&M tasks, which are currently performed by human

operators, thus improving safety and reducing risk exposure for O&M workers. Case studies [50] and [51] focus on improving the operational efficiency and reliability of PV systems and microgrids by detecting and locating faults. Common issues between the two case studies include the difficulty of accurately detecting faults in real-time under various environmental conditions, such as temperature and irradiance or varying loads in microgrids. These conditions can make faults or anomalies difficult to distinguish from normal system behaviour. In both cases, traditional fault detection methods often require expensive hardware and can be inefficient in large-scale systems, as the faults can arise in multiple components simultaneously. Also, the large volume of sensor data generated by multiple monitoring points in the systems presents a challenge, as it requires efficient data processing and management to ensure real-time fault detection and classification without overwhelming the system. To address these challenges, both technologies rely on ANNs to classify and locate faults. They aim to minimize the number of sensors used to locate faults, reducing operational costs and maintenance requirements. The work of [50] focuses on specific electrical faults in a PV system, such as open circuits, short circuits, degradation, and partial shading. The solution proposed uses real-time SCADA data integrated with a trained ANN model to predict voltage and current, detect faults, classify them, and identify the exact location of faulty panels. The method also accurately locates the faulty panels using a predefined range for voltage sensors, which reduces the need for extensive hardware installations. On the other hand, [51] deals with a hybrid microgrid system that integrates PV systems with other energy sources like BESSs. It integrates real-time monitoring and data from the microgrid system to detect faults promptly, leveraging data-driven models to accurately classify and locate faults based on predefined features and thresholds. The ANN's ability to learn from historical data and make predictions based on real-time inputs offers a robust solution to detect faults without an extensive sensor infrastructure, reducing maintenance costs and improving system reliability. In both cases, some restrictions regarding the quality and quantity of data required to train the ANN model must be considered. The model's accuracy depends heavily on the quality of the input data, which sensor malfunctions or environmental conditions may impact. If the dataset does not represent all possible fault scenarios, the model's performance could degrade. Additionally, when scaling this approach for larger and more complex systems, the number of variables to be processed will increase significantly and it may require more optimization algorithms.

The integration of AI with traditional fault detection and location methods is proving to be highly beneficial in improving the efficiency of renewable energy systems, particularly in PV systems. AI-based solutions not only enable

early detection and faster diagnosis but also optimize the overall operation and maintenance processes, thus improving system reliability and reducing operational costs. AI-based approaches have been instrumental in identifying anomalies and out-of-normal conditions in critical PV system components such as modules, cables, inverters, and transformers. However, despite the significant progress, field-implemented solutions still often require human intervention for diagnosis and fault location, especially in real-world applications.

4.4. Data-driven decision systems components

The global energy sector is undergoing transformative changes driven by net-zero emission targets and the widespread electrification of various industries. These changes demand the adoption of data-driven decision systems that integrate advanced modelling, scenario analysis, and large-scale data integration. The use of electricity by many sectors of our society has significantly increased the complexity of energy systems. This demand is expected to rise even further in the coming decades which creates the necessity of innovative methods to manage and optimize energy flows while anticipating future challenges and opportunities. Renewable energy must be the cornerstone of global efforts to meet the Paris Agreement's goals of reducing greenhouse gas emissions and limiting the rise in global temperature, with the COP 29 recently reinforcing the necessity of those efforts.

Figure 7 - Power generation and greenhouse gas emissions in Europe. [52]

Figure 8 - Carbon Neutrality Roadmap 2050: The consolidated path to corporate sustainability [53]. The European Green Deal aims to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 55% by 2030, compared to 1990 levels, and achieve climate neutrality by 2050. The goals include increasing energy efficiency (by 32,5% by 2030), promoting renewable energy (by 42.5% by 2030).

The need of reliable models capable of covering the complexities of energy flows, such as spatial factors and long periods of time, is one of the main challenges that data-driven decision-making in energy systems have to face. The GENeSYS-MOD, an open-source energy system model developed within the European OpenENTRANCE project, exemplifies such approach. This cost-optimization model integrates renewable energy technologies, energy storage systems, and sectoral coupling to simulate energy transitions under decarbonization constraints. The model's flexibility in geographic and temporal scales, ranging from local to global, makes it an invaluable tool for policymakers and decision-makers aiming to evaluate net-zero pathways. For instance, the model has been instrumental in identifying decarbonization strategies for Europe, helping stakeholders to better understand the impacts of energy efficiency measures, renewable integration, and grid flexibility requirements [54].

Figure 9 - Global Energy System Model (GENeSYS-MOD) [54]

A key challenge in developing such models lies in the integration of diverse data sources. Data must encompass technical, social, economic, and environmental dimensions to accurately reflect the many types of energy systems that together complement each other towards the energy transition. The European Union's "Going Climate Neutral by 2050" initiative underscores the importance of comprehensive data collection and integration. According to this initiative, data-driven frameworks must support scenario-building exercises that allow policymakers to evaluate the trade-offs and synergies between different strategies. Such scenarios often involve optimizing energy mixes, balancing local renewable resources, and minimizing the costs associated with energy transitions [55].

Another critical component of these decision systems is the ability to manage uncertainties and dynamic changes within energy systems. Studies on Bayesian analysis demonstrates how Bayesian frameworks can be employed to quantify uncertainties and incorporate them into energy planning models, helping with the decisions taken by the supports systems. This approach is particularly useful for anticipating variations in renewable energy generation, such as fluctuations in wind and solar power output, and for evaluating the robustness of different strategies under various future scenarios. By leveraging probabilistic models, decision-makers can gain insights into the reliability of energy systems and identify strategies that perform well across a range of uncertain conditions [56].

Emerging technologies, such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), further enhance the capabilities of data-driven decision systems. Research on energy systems an AI integration highlights how AI can optimize energy systems by processing large datasets, detecting patterns, and enabling predictive analytics. AI-driven tools are increasingly being used to forecast energy demand, optimize grid operations, and enhance the integration of distributed energy resources (DERs). For example, AI-based decision systems can dynamically adjust energy flows to match real-time conditions, improving grid stability and minimizing energy losses. Additionally, these systems enable the proactive identification of potential disruptions, allowing operators to implement preventative measures and reduce downtime [57].

Figure 10 - Model for decision making system [57]

The study conducted in Italy is an example of how these tools can be applied, helping to create models that can predict the necessities and complexities of energy flow. This study employs optimization frameworks to explore decarbonization strategies that align with Italy's national energy targets. By integrating renewable energy sources, storage systems, and sector coupling, the research identifies cost-effective pathways to achieve carbon neutrality while addressing economic and technical constraints. The study emphasizes the importance of scenario analysis and the use of detailed temporal and spatial modelling to manage energy flows and meet long-term policy goals [58].

European projects such as OpenENTRANCE and initiatives led by the European Commission play a vital role in advancing data-driven decision systems. OpenENTRANCE, for instance, focuses on creating open-source models and tools to support the development of low-carbon energy systems. The project's emphasis on transparency and collaboration ensures that stakeholders from academia, industry, and government can contribute to and benefit from its

findings [54]. Similarly, the European Commission's strategy for climate neutrality by 2050 highlights the integration of digital and data-driven technologies as a cornerstone for achieving sustainable energy transitions. These efforts align with global trends in smart grid development and the increasing adoption of IoT-enabled energy monitoring systems [55].

Despite these advancements, several challenges remain. One significant issue is the durability and inter-operability of data systems across different regions and stakeholders. For instance, ensuring that models like GENE SYS-MOD can seamlessly integrate data from various national grids requires standardized data formats and robust communication protocols. Additionally, the reliance on large datasets and complex algorithms introduces ethical considerations, such as data privacy and the potential for algorithmic biases. Addressing these challenges requires coordinated efforts among policymakers, researchers, and industry leaders to establish clear guidelines and best practices for data governance in energy systems [56].

The Sørsida development in Ålesund serves as a prominent example of how data-driven decision-making can align urban development with ambitious decarbonization goals [59]. Predictive models and impact analysis tools have been instrumental for defining strategies and identifying Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that track critical information such as greenhouse gas emissions reductions, energy efficiency, and sustainable mobility. These tools allow us to simulate various development scenarios and assess the environmental, economic, and social impacts of different strategies over time. KPIs are not limited to emissions; they also encompass indicators like public transport accessibility, cycling infrastructure usage, and the proportion of adaptive reuse in building projects. The use of frameworks such as NEB-Compass further supports this process by integrating data across environmental, social, and economic dimensions to ensure that the trade-offs between development and sustainability are managed effectively. By employing these tools, Ålesund aims to reduce emissions by 60% by 2030 while fostering a vibrant and livable urban space [59].

The Sørsida project faces notable challenges that reflect broader issues in sustainable urban development. A major one has been reconciling outdated zoning plans with modern climate and sustainability objectives. The original 2015 zoning plan, for example, emphasized large-scale demolition of existing buildings to make way for new construction, a practice that conflicts with contemporary principles of circular economy and adaptive reuse. Another challenge lies in transforming mobility patterns in a city historically dominated by cars. The lack of dedicated infrastructure for cyclists and pedestrians, compounded by limited public transportation options, has hindered efforts to promote low-carbon mobility. To address these limitations, Ålesund has

implemented solutions such as a new public transport hub, safer pedestrian crossings, and temporary bicycle repair and rental facilities. These measures are designed to shift reliance away from cars and foster a culture of sustainable transport, which is critical to reducing the city's emissions from road traffic, one of its largest sources [59].

At the heart of Sørsida's strategy is the adaptive reuse of existing buildings and the integration of temporary infrastructure as a testing ground for sustainable solutions. The transformation of the Devold building into a skate hall and cultural space exemplifies this approach, demonstrating how older structures can be repurposed to reduce construction-related emissions while preserving the area's historical and cultural identity. Temporary infrastructure, such as movable recreation areas and experimental waste-sorting initiatives, allows for iterative development, enabling planners to refine strategies based on real-world outcomes before committing to permanent installations. Feasibility studies have also played a critical role in refining solutions, including plans for electric bike rentals, stormwater management using blue-green infrastructure, and optimized building orientations to account for climate adaptation needs such as storm surges and heavy rainfall [59]. By embedding these adaptive, participatory, and data-driven methods into its planning processes, Sørsida not only aligns urban development with decarbonization goals but also serves as a replicable model for cities facing similar challenges.

In conclusion, data-driven decision systems are indispensable for navigating the complexities of modern energy systems and achieving net-zero emissions. By leveraging advanced models like GENeSYS-MOD, integrating cutting-edge technologies such as AI, and fostering international collaboration through initiatives like OpenENTRANCE, stakeholders can develop effective strategies to optimize energy systems and address emerging challenges. As these systems continue to evolve, ongoing research and innovation will be essential to ensure their reliability, scalability, and accessibility, paving the way for a sustainable energy future.

5. State of the Art: Summary Tables

5.1. Sensor Technologies

Sensor Technologies

Challenges: The offshore renewable energy sector faces several significant challenges. One primary issue is dealing with extreme environmental conditions, which cause wear and tear on structures and components, necessitating robust designs and monitoring systems. Additionally, bad weather and storms can make reaching the offshore structures practically impossible. Another challenge is the high operational and maintenance costs, which can constitute up to 25–30% of total lifecycle costs, driven by the harsh marine environment. Ensuring structural integrity is critical, especially with larger turbines that introduce new forces on foundations. Effective monitoring systems are essential to detect damages early, particularly for underwater components and floating platforms. Additionally, sensor durability is compromised by prolonged exposure to marine conditions, biofouling, and corrosion, requiring protective measures. Lastly, complex interactions between wave energy converters (WECs) and port infrastructure highlight the need for advanced monitoring systems to evaluate hydrodynamic forces and ensure stability and energy efficiency.

Solutions: Advanced state-of-health (SOH) monitoring systems enable remote control and condition-based maintenance, allowing real-time structural integrity assessments and reducing downtime. Integration of advanced sensors, such as vibration, acoustic emission, and pressure sensors, improves structural monitoring and hydrodynamic performance evaluation. Hybrid Power Take-Off (PTO) systems, combining triboelectric and electromagnetic technologies, are proposed to enhance energy conversion efficiency in variable marine conditions. Model Predictive Control (MPC) techniques optimize energy capture in WECs by adapting to dynamic environments in real-time. Protective measures, like sensor coatings and calibration, mitigate marine condition effects, while robust designs improve resilience. Lastly, the Hardware-In-The-Loop (HIL) methodology combines real and simulated components for efficient testing under extreme conditions, reducing costs and improving operational performance.

Limitations: Despite advancements, several limitations hinder the offshore renewable energy sector. Sensor durability remains a critical issue, as biofouling and corrosion in marine environments reduce their lifespan and accuracy, necessitating regular calibration and protective measures. Noise interference significantly affects vibration sensors, complicating fault diagnosis for mechanical components like gearboxes. Data processing for advanced diagnostic systems, particularly those using machine learning algorithms like CNNs and LSTMs, requires substantial computational resources, which can be challenging in remote offshore locations with

limited connectivity. The accuracy of control models in MPC techniques is another limitation; errors in parameters like mass and stiffness can cause inefficiencies and instability. Finally, capturing and interpreting real-time data for complex hydrodynamic interactions between WECs and structural elements is challenging, further complicating stability evaluations.

Overlap and comparison between solutions: The proposed solutions demonstrate significant overlap and interconnection in addressing the sector's challenges. Advanced state-of-health monitoring systems and sensor integration both rely on real-time data to assess structural integrity and detect potential issues, emphasizing their complementary roles in condition-based maintenance strategies. Model Predictive Control (MPC) and real-time feedback systems depend on sensor data to optimize energy capture and ensure operational stability in dynamic marine environments. Hybrid systems, like PTO mechanisms, align with robust design strategies, focusing on improving energy conversion efficiency and resilience under varying conditions. Solutions targeting noise interference, and the integration of machine learning algorithms also overlap, highlighting a shared goal of enhancing diagnostic accuracy and system reliability. Together, these approaches reflect a comprehensive strategy to enhance reliability, efficiency, and operational effectiveness in offshore renewable energy systems.

Technical Perspective: Technically, vibration and acoustic sensors play a crucial role in monitoring structural integrity and detecting issues like material fatigue, although they are vulnerable to noise interference. Pressure sensors provide vital data on hydrodynamic forces, crucial for optimizing WECs and hybrid systems, but require robust designs to withstand biofouling and corrosion. Machine learning algorithms, such as CNNs and LSTMs, enhance fault diagnosis and improve sensor data interpretation under noisy conditions. MPC techniques enable dynamic optimization of energy capture by leveraging real-time data, though their success depends on accurate system models.

Operational Perspective: Operationally, condition-based maintenance strategies reduce costs and downtime by enabling timely repairs based on real-time monitoring. Remote operations and data acquisition systems are essential for overseeing energy generation and structural integrity in inaccessible offshore locations. Sensor designs must adapt to harsh marine environments, employing protective measures to maintain functionality. Multi-functional integration of WECs with coastal infrastructure maximizes utility while addressing coastal protection needs. Finally, personnel training is vital to ensure operators can effectively manage advanced monitoring systems and make informed decisions.

5.2. Data and model interoperability components

Data and model interoperability components

Challenges: This section identifies several challenges related to the implementation of the Common Information Model (CIM) in modern power systems. First, there are difficulties in achieving real-time data processing and maintaining system stability, especially under heavy data loads. Second, a lack of a standardized framework for data exchange leads to inefficiencies and interoperability issues, hindering seamless communication between different system components. Third, scalability and integration pose challenges, particularly with advanced technologies like Building Information Models (BIM) and distributed energy systems. Fourth, the management of measurement errors is complicated by uncertainties, especially in multi-Digital Twin environments, impacting decision-making processes. Lastly, traditional methods for automating and synchronizing Power Quality (PQ) activities across systems remain resource-intensive, necessitating a more streamlined approach. Beyond interoperability and digital co-simulation, another key challenge in modern power grids is ensuring fault resilience and predictive maintenance. As electricity networks evolve to accommodate more renewable energy and digital technologies, advanced machine learning techniques are becoming essential for identifying faults in real time.

Solutions: It was proposed several solutions aimed at enhancing the efficiency and adaptability of CIM. Standardized architectures and open frameworks are recommended to improve system integration and compatibility, facilitating better data exchange between Transmission System Operators (TSOs) and Distribution System Operators (DSOs). The application of IEC standards (IEC 61970-301 and IEC 61968-11) is suggested for a unified data representation, improving data storage and retrieval. Advanced data models and algorithms, including predictive analytics and scalable cloud-based solutions, can support real-time synchronization and demand-response management. AI and machine learning integration is emphasized to enable large-scale data processing, predictive analysis, and dynamic adaptability. Enhanced database functionality, such as implementing sophisticated SQL commands and automated CIM RDF file generation, is also proposed. Additionally, incorporating social data into the CIM framework can improve renewable energy management, while interoperable interfaces can streamline utility operations across diverse applications. AI-driven fault detection, integrated with CIM-based digital twins, enhances power system stability by predicting failures in high-voltage networks, transformers, and renewable energy systems. Deep learning methods such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks play a crucial role in analysing electrical signals and detecting anomalies.

Limitations: Despite its potential, CIM faces significant limitations in modern power systems. Scalability remains a key issue, particularly when integrating

Distributed Energy Resources (DERs) and Digital Twin technologies in large and complex systems. Gaps in CIM's integration with Building Information Models (BIM) hinder visualization and management capabilities in energy projects. Achieving real-time data processing under heavy loads is another major challenge, resulting in operational inefficiencies. Measurement and error management is difficult, especially in environments relying on Digital Twins, where accuracy is critical for decision-making. Automation processes for Power Quality (PQ) activities are resource-intensive and need more effective solutions to optimize performance. Furthermore, CIM lacks support for advanced visualizations, such as 3D simulations, which are becoming increasingly important for managing complex infrastructure. Another limitation arises in the deployment of ML and AI for fault classification. The identification of relevant features is crucial, as relying solely on basic statistical features does not yield high classification accuracy, while excessive dependence on ML-based feature extraction without prior knowledge compromises generalization. Poor training data quality also affects model robustness.

Overlap and comparison between solutions: The solutions proposed in the paper exhibit significant overlap, with many addressing interconnected issues. For instance, standardized architectures and interoperable interfaces both aim to enhance integration and data sharing between systems, fostering a cohesive environment for power management. Similarly, the development of advanced data models and the integration of AI/ML technologies both focus on improving system responsiveness, predictive capabilities, and real-time adaptability. Enhanced database functionality complements these by supporting the automation of data processes and ensuring reliable storage and retrieval. Furthermore, the incorporation of social data aligns with the need for improved modeling and visualizations, enabling a more comprehensive understanding of energy systems. Real-time data processing enhancements and measurement error management also share a link, as better data handling reduces inaccuracies and improves reliability. By recognizing these overlaps, it is evident that these solutions collectively form a cohesive framework to address CIM's challenges effectively. Moreover, recent research has focused on leveraging ensemble learning techniques, such as bagging, boosting, and stacking, in combination with deep neural networks to enhance time-series fault classification performance in power systems and industrial applications. These methods improve prediction accuracy and robustness, particularly in noisy environments.

Technical Perspective: From a technical standpoint, CIM provides several advantages. It standardizes data formats and structures, ensuring seamless communication between different systems and stakeholders. Its modular architecture allows for the integration of diverse components, enabling the modeling of complex scenarios and supporting multiple applications simultaneously. CIM also supports advanced data modeling, representing complex relationships within power systems, such as interactions between

generation, transmission, and distribution networks. Furthermore, its compatibility with AI and ML applications enhances predictive analytics and smart decision-making, while its framework accommodates renewable energy sources, facilitating their integration into power grids. In addition, recent research has proposed hybrid deep learning approaches for fault classification in electrical systems, combining automated feature extraction with statistical methods to improve classification accuracy. The use of second-generation wavelet decomposition theory, adaptive latent features (ALFs), and gradient boosting classifiers has further advanced the fault detection capabilities of machine learning-based models.

Operational Perspective: Operationally, CIM improves coordination among operators, particularly between TSOs and DSOs, leading to more efficient decision-making and system resilience. It enables greater automation, such as in Power Quality (PQ) monitoring, reducing labour intensity and streamlining processes. Its real-time monitoring capabilities enhance grid reliability by allowing for immediate operational adjustments in response to disturbances. CIM's adherence to international standards fosters interoperability across legacy and modern systems, ensuring smooth integration. However, challenges remain, including the need for extensive training, workflow adjustments, and continuous improvements in scalability and advanced visualizations. Additionally, recent research in fault detection and post-fault operations of power electronics has highlighted the importance of fault-tolerant strategies in power converters, particularly in multilevel modular converters (MMCs). Open-circuit faults in MMCs can go unnoticed for extended periods, leading to secondary faults and system malfunctions. Fault detection and localization (FDL) techniques, along with fault-tolerant (FT) strategies, are critical for enhancing the reliability of these systems. Studies have shown that conventional least-squares signal-based FDL techniques can be affected by modulation techniques and voltage balancing algorithms, making fault detection challenging under certain conditions. Various control strategies utilizing neutral shift have been proposed to maintain stable post-fault operation in MMCs, improving system reliability and ensuring continued functionality despite switch failures. These aspects underscore CIM's critical role in advancing power systems while highlighting areas for further enhancement.

5.3. Digital asset information components

Digital asset information components

Challenges: The document identifies key challenges in leveraging AI for renewable energy systems, particularly photovoltaic (PV) systems. One major issue is the imbalance in datasets, where fault-free conditions dominate, leading to potential overfitting in machine learning (ML) models. The quality of data is another critical challenge, as sensor malfunctions or environmental noise can degrade AI model performance. Synthetic data generated by digital twins (DT) helps train models but may not fully represent all fault scenarios, limiting generalizability. The large volumes of real-time

data increase processing times, impacting fault detection efficiency. Integration with existing infrastructures presents challenges in managing data integrity and computational load. Finally, environmental variability, such as fluctuating temperatures and irradiance, adds complexity, introducing noise and variability that AI models must address. Tackling these challenges is crucial for the effective application of AI in renewable energy systems.

Solutions: To address these challenges, the state of the art proposes various solutions aimed at improving fault detection and operational efficiency in PV systems. Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) are widely used to classify and locate faults, reducing the need for extensive sensors and minimizing operational costs. Data-driven models combine real-time monitoring with historical data to promptly identify faults, leveraging predefined features for accuracy. Drone-based thermal imaging enables detection of hotspots and bypass diode failures, while Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) systems streamline data processing, improving automation and reliability. Digital twins simulate fault scenarios, enhance predictive maintenance, and facilitate real-time fault detection. Machine learning algorithms, such as Random Forests and k-Nearest Neighbors, are employed to analyze inverter data and improve fault classification. These solutions collectively enhance system reliability, safety, and cost-effectiveness in renewable energy operations.

Limitations: Despite advancements, several limitations remain in applying AI to renewable energy systems. Many AI-driven solutions still require human intervention for diagnosing and locating faults, limiting full automation. Thermal imaging, while effective, faces challenges from shadows, panel edge visibility, and altitude variations, reducing accuracy. Synthetic data generated by digital twins does not always represent all fault scenarios, affecting model generalizability. Traditional fault detection methods rely on expensive hardware and are inefficient for large-scale systems. AI integration requires significant computational resources, posing challenges for real-time processing in remote or resource-limited environments. Lastly, environmental variability introduces additional noise and complexity, making it harder for AI models to differentiate normal fluctuations from actual faults. These limitations highlight the need for further research to improve AI's robustness and scalability in renewable energy systems.

Overlap and comparison between solutions: The proposed solutions exhibit significant overlap and synergies, reflecting a comprehensive approach to improving fault detection in PV systems. Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) are central to both case studies, showcasing their widespread use for fault classification and operational efficiency. Thermal imaging is frequently paired with inverter data to enhance robustness, with the former detecting visual anomalies and the latter addressing electrical issues. Digital twins are used across approaches, either to generate synthetic training data or to facilitate real-time monitoring and predictive maintenance. SCADA systems

are a common thread, serving as a foundational data source for anomaly detection and operational automation. Machine learning algorithms like Random Forests and k-Nearest Neighbors complement these solutions by improving fault classification and efficiency. These overlaps emphasize the importance of combining advanced AI techniques, real-time data integration, and robust fault detection mechanisms to optimize PV system performance.

Technical Perspective: Machine learning techniques, including ANNs and Random Forests, are critical for analyzing complex data and identifying fault patterns. Thermal imaging, particularly drone-based, provides high-resolution analyses to detect hotspot faults, though it is sensitive to environmental variables like shadows. Digital twins simulate system performance under various conditions, aiding in fault prediction and maintenance optimization. SCADA data integration enhances real-time monitoring and fault detection, offering a comprehensive view of system performance. However, handling large volumes of real-time data remains a challenge, requiring optimized algorithms to ensure efficient processing and timely detection.

Operational Perspective: AI-driven solutions enable automation of operations and maintenance (O&M), improving safety and reducing human error. Predictive maintenance lowers costs and downtime by identifying faults early, extending asset lifespans. Real-time data analysis facilitates rapid decision-making, ensuring minimal disruption to operations. However, the effectiveness of these solutions depends on the quality and representativeness of training data, as biases or inaccuracies can compromise model performance. Environmental variability, such as changes in temperature and irradiance, complicates fault detection, requiring strategies to distinguish between normal fluctuations and genuine faults. These particularities highlight the interplay between advanced technology and practical operational strategies, emphasizing the need for continual improvement to fully realize AI's potential in renewable energy systems.

5.4. Data-driven decision systems components

Data-driven decision systems components

Challenges: The state of the art identifies critical challenges in developing data-driven decision systems to support energy transitions. First, integrating diverse data sources—technical, social, economic, and environmental—is necessary to capture the complexity of energy systems, but achieving seamless integration remains difficult. Managing uncertainties, especially in renewable energy systems with fluctuating generation, requires advanced probabilistic models like Bayesian frameworks to quantify and address variability. Ensuring the durability and interoperability of data systems across regions and stakeholders demands standardized formats and robust

communication protocols, which are challenging to implement. Ethical considerations, including data privacy and algorithmic biases, pose governance challenges as systems increasingly rely on large datasets and complex algorithms. Finally, the increasing complexity of energy flows, driven by widespread electrification and renewable energy integration, requires innovative methods to optimize and manage these dynamic systems. Overcoming these challenges is vital for achieving net-zero emissions through effective data-driven approaches.

Solutions: The document identifies critical challenges in developing data-driven decision systems to support energy transitions. First, integrating diverse data sources—technical, social, economic, and environmental—is necessary to capture the complexity of energy systems, but achieving seamless integration remains difficult. Managing uncertainties, especially in renewable energy systems with fluctuating generation, requires advanced probabilistic models like Bayesian frameworks to quantify and address variability. Ensuring the durability and interoperability of data systems across regions and stakeholders demands standardized formats and robust communication protocols, which are challenging to implement. Ethical considerations, including data privacy and algorithmic biases, pose governance challenges as systems increasingly rely on large datasets and complex algorithms. Finally, the increasing complexity of energy flows, driven by widespread electrification and renewable energy integration, requires innovative methods to optimize and manage these dynamic systems. Overcoming these challenges is vital for achieving net-zero emissions through effective data-driven approaches.

Limitations: Several limitations hinder the effectiveness of data-driven decision systems in energy transitions. The complexity of modern energy systems, exacerbated by electrification and renewable energy integration, presents challenges for accurate modeling and optimization. Data durability and interoperability issues complicate the integration of systems across regions and stakeholders, as standardized formats are not universally implemented. Ethical concerns, including data privacy and algorithmic biases, require governance frameworks to mitigate risks. The integration of diverse data sources remains challenging, as technical, social, economic, and environmental datasets must be cohesively managed. Uncertainty in renewable energy generation adds another layer of complexity, with variability in wind and solar outputs making long-term planning difficult. Additionally, the reliance on advanced technologies like AI necessitates continuous updates, system maintenance, and skilled personnel for data analysis, increasing operational demands. These limitations underscore the need for further development and refinement to ensure the reliability and inclusivity of data-driven decision systems.

Overlap and comparison between solutions: The solutions proposed for data-driven decision systems exhibit significant overlap, indicating their interconnectedness in addressing energy transition challenges. Open-

source models like GENeSYS-MOD and comprehensive data collection share a focus on collaboration and inclusivity, with the former emphasizing transparency and the latter prioritizing diverse data integration. Scenario analysis and Bayesian decision support systems both tackle uncertainty but differ in approach: scenario analysis explores multiple strategic outcomes, while Bayesian methods incorporate probabilistic models to quantify uncertainties. AI integration complements optimization frameworks by automating data processing and enhancing predictive capabilities, enabling dynamic adjustments in energy systems. Standardizing data formats and implementing ethical guidelines both aim to improve interoperability and governance, with the former addressing technical barriers and the latter ensuring fairness and trust in data usage. Ongoing research and innovation support all solutions by driving advancements and adapting systems to evolving challenges. Together, these solutions provide a cohesive framework for optimizing energy systems and achieving climate goals.

Technical Perspective: The technical aspects of these systems revolve around advanced modeling, data integration, and computational tools. In the Sørsida case, it leverages data-driven decision-making tools to track KPIs such as greenhouse gas emissions, energy efficiency, and mobility improvements. Predictive models and frameworks like NEB-Compass integrate environmental, social, and economic data to simulate development scenarios and assess impacts. Innovative solutions, such as blue-green infrastructure for stormwater management, enhance climate adaptation efforts. Models like GENeSYS-MOD are highly flexible, allowing for simulations of energy transitions on both local and global scales, incorporating cost-optimization and renewable energy technologies. Effective integration of diverse data types—technical, social, economic, and environmental—is critical, requiring sophisticated systems that can manage and harmonize various data formats dynamically. AI and machine learning enhance these systems by detecting patterns, enabling predictive analytics, and optimizing grid operations and energy demand forecasting. Bayesian frameworks provide probabilistic approaches to quantify uncertainties in renewable energy generation and demand, aiding in adaptive energy planning. However, processing the large volumes of real-time data required for these systems remains a significant challenge, necessitating optimized algorithms to ensure timely and accurate analysis.

Operational Perspective: Operationally, these systems depend on collaboration, robust governance, and continuous innovation. Stakeholder collaboration among governments, academia, and industry is essential to ensure successful implementation and resource sharing. Scenario analysis serves as a practical decision-making tool, enabling policymakers to evaluate trade-offs and optimize energy mixes by modeling various outcomes. Interoperability challenges, such as establishing consistent communication protocols and standardized data formats, must be addressed to facilitate seamless data integration across regions and systems.

Ethical considerations, including data privacy and algorithmic bias, are crucial for building trust and ensuring fairness in decision-making processes. Continuous research and innovation are necessary to adapt operational frameworks to evolving technologies and challenges, ensuring that these systems remain reliable, scalable, and effective.

6. Strengths, Opportunities, and Shared Characteristics of the Use Cases

6.1. Strengths and Opportunities of Each Use Case

Use case 1

(Ålesund, Norway and Mindelo, Cape Verde)

Use Case 1 combines two very different locations with curious common features, enabling them to address their challenges in a coordinated manner. Both are major ports, part of electrical islands and have abundant renewable resources that can help supply power to docked vessels.

Table 1 - Strengths and Opportunities for Use Case 1

Strengths	Opportunities
Two locations on two continents, both fishing, cargo and cruise ports, expanding their operation wind/PV in CV)	Develop renewable energy integration in islanded networks
Renewable energy sources availability (hydro in Norway	Develop seamless integration of OPS
Islanded operation	

Use case 2

(EDP, Portugal - site: Villacastin and Cruz del Hierro, Spain)

Use Case 2 features a state-of-the-art solar PV farm in a region with high year-round solar irradiance, where AI supports operation and maintenance.

Table 2 - Strengths and Opportunities for Use Case 2

Strengths	Opportunities
Vast experience in operating large grid-connected PV parks	Further development of fault detection and classification
Experience with fault detection and location	Enhance PV system modelling
State-of-the-art technology	

Use case 3

(Sigma WEC, Slovenia – site: Montenegro)

Use case 3 combines an offshore-deployed wave energy converter prototype with a large number of sensors and communication capabilities, making it an offshore laboratory.

Table 3 - Strengths and Opportunities for Use Case 3

Major points	Opportunities
Novel/experimental technology (WEC)	Collect and analyse real operation data
Medium-scale deployed prototype developed by a tech company	Assess the behaviour of a laboratory-tested prototype in a real deployment
High level of sensing and real-time data link	

Use case 4

(Brazil)

Use case 4 brings co-simulation of renewable energy sources integration to the project and aims to interact with grid information, expanding the reach of simulation tools.

Table 4 - Strengths and Opportunities for Use Case 4

Major points	Opportunities
Experience in co-simulation applied to renewable energy integration	Combine co-simulation with grid integration
Interaction with Brazil System Operator	Expand the application of tested co-simulation approaches to other sites
Advanced laboratory facilities	

Use case 5

(Canada)

Use case 5 addresses renewable energy integration from the point of view of generation (machine vibration) and consumption (impact of distributed generation and EV integration on power system).

Table 5 - Strengths and Opportunities for Use Case 5

Major points	Opportunities
Experience in using data-centric solutions for renewable energy integration	Expand the application of data-centric solutions to address renewable energy integration
Expertise in power electronics and modelling the impact of DER and EV integration on power system.	Apply different simulations and tests on several benchmarking models and systems
Advanced laboratory facilities	

6.2. Common Features and Interconnections Across Use Cases

While digital twin integration is the most significant common ground of the various use cases, there are other overlapping features. The following figure highlights some of these interconnections.

Figure 11 - Interconnections Across Use Cases

7. Conclusions and next steps

The deliverable D2.3 "Use Case Requirements" for the ORION project outlines all the requirements and methodologies for the project's use cases. These use cases span diverse geographical locations and technological applications, each contributing to the overarching goal of enhancing renewable energy integration and digitalization within the energy sector.

The analysis of the use cases reveals a focus on port decarbonization in Norway and Cape Verde, operational efficiency of large-scale photovoltaic plants in Portugal/Spain, early fault detection in floating offshore wave energy converters in Slovenia, geographically distributed co-simulation infrastructure in Brazil, and data-centric solutions for power generation and distribution in Canada. Each use case presents unique strengths and opportunities, such as the integration of renewable energy sources, advanced fault detection methods, and the application of co-simulation techniques.

Furthermore, this deliverable provides an exhaustive review of current technologies and methodologies in sensor technologies, data and model interoperability, digital asset information components, and data-driven decision systems. It highlights the strengths, opportunities, and shared characteristics across the use cases, emphasizing the role of digital twins and AI in optimizing energy systems.

The deliverable is a living document, considering that all use cases will be further refined throughout the next months, in a straight collaboration between WPs two, three and four. The implementation and testing of the defined use cases, will be made alongside regular updates and enhancements based on feedback and new insights provided by the UCs owners.

Stakeholder engagement with all the actors identified in this deliverable will remain a priority to ensure alignment with project objectives and facilitate knowledge exchange.

References

- [1] Global Wind Energy Council (GWEC) (2022). Gwec global offshore wind report 2022. Retrieved from [https://gwec.net/gwecs-global-offshore-wind-report/\(14.09.2022\)](https://gwec.net/gwecs-global-offshore-wind-report/(14.09.2022)).
- [2] GWEC. Regional onshore and offshore wind outlook for new installations (gwec)., 2023. Retrieved from <https://gwec.net/globalwindreport2023/>.
- [3] H. Braam L. Rademakers J. Xiang S. Watson E. Wiggelinkhuizen, T. Verbruggen. Assessment of condition monitoring techniques for offshore wind farms. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.2931512>.
- [4] Retrieved from <https://noctula.pt/projeto-windfloat-atlantic-primeiro-parque-eolico-maritimo-em-portug>
- [5] Retrieved from <https://engenhariae.com.br/energia/aws-atinge-marco-do-conversor-de-energia-das-ondas>.
- [6] S.M. Muyeen M.L. Hossain, A. Abu-Siada. Methods for advanced wind turbine condition monitoring and early diagnosis: A literature review. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.3390/en11051309>.
- [7] IEEE Xuanrui Huang Zechuan Lin, Student Member, IEEE Xi Xiao Fellow IEEE Nilkamjon S. Ratreng Alessandro Molle John V. Ringwood, Member, and Carlo Grazianetti. A sensitivity analysis of wave energy converter model predictive control systems with wave excitation force estimation and prediction. Retrieved from <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10700048>.
- [8] Ziyue Xi Shu Dai Fuzhen Xing Hao Wang, Jiajing Sun and Minyi Xu. Recent progress on built-in wave energy converters: A review. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse12071176>.
- [9] Mário J.G. C. Mendes Mojtaba Kamarlouei C. Guedes Soares Jos´e F. Gaspar, Rafael F. Pinheiro. Review on hardware-in-the-loop simulation of wave energy converters and power take-offs. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2023.114144>.
- [10] IEEE Ted K. A. Brekken Alan Fern Senior Member IEEE Leila Ghorban Zadeh, Member and IEEE Member IEEE Ali Haider Shahbaz, Senior Member. Hardware in the loop wave energy converter control under control faults and model mismatch. Retrieved from <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10122770>.
- [11] Li Shen Mingxin Li Jichuan Kanga, Xu Zhu. Fault diagnosis of a wave energy converter gearbox based on an adam optimized cnn-lstm algorithm. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2024.121022>.
- [12] Paulo Jorge Rosa Santos Francisco de Almeida Taveira Pinto. Retrieved from <https://dec.fe.up.pt/projetos/nano-tecnologias-inovadoras-para-conversao-de-energia-das-ondas>.
- [13] Retrieved from <https://noticias.up.pt/2021/03/08/cientistas-da-u-porto-criam-dispositivos-que-geram-en>
- [14] Tom´as Calheiros-Cabral; Victor Ramos; Gianmaria Giannini; Beatriz Queir´os; Paulo Rosa-Santos; Francisco Taveira-Pinto. Avalia_c~ao do impacto de um conversor de energia das ondas integrado num quebra-mar portu´ario. Retrieved from <https://pianc.pt/wpcontent/uploads/2023/10/Artigo-53.pdf>.
- [15] <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.1850485>

- [16] <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIE.2016.2571258>
- [17] Ref <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2014.10.010>
- [18] <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2012.08.072>
- [19] <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2016.05.085>
- [20] <http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2015/139695>
- [21] <https://doi.org/10.3390/s24020543>
- [22] doi:10.1088/1742-6596/2257/1/012008
- [23] A. Bytyqi, S. Gandhi, E. Lambert, and N. Petrović, "A review on tso-dso data exchange, cim extensions and interoperability aspects," *Journal of Modern Power Systems and Clean Energy*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 309–315, 2022.
- [24] V. M. Balijepalli, F. Sielker, and G. Karmakar, "Evolution of power system cim to digital twins - a comprehensive review and analysis," in *2021 IEEE PES Innovative Smart Grid Technologies Europe (ISGT Europe)*, 2021, pp. 1–6.
- [25] L. Zhijun, H. Kewei, Z. Yuguang, S. Ning, and S. Yuanliang, "Thinking of common information model of digital power system," in *2023 5th Asia Energy and Electrical Engineering Symposium (AEEES)*, 2023, pp.471–476.
- [26] X. Fan, J. Wang, W. Qiu, R. Sun, R. Ding, Y. Sun, Y. Wu, and S. Pi, "Common information model for social data extended by iec 62325 environmental package and its application in renewable energy accommodation," in *2022 IEEE 5th International Conference on Electronics Technology (ICET)*, 2022, pp. 1060–1064.
- [27] T. Cooke and T. Laughner, "Using the common information model for power quality data," in *2023 IEEE Power Energy Society General Meeting (PESGM)*, 2023, pp. 1–3.
- [28] Y. Wang and P. Sai, "Design and optimization of an intelligent monitoring system for overhead lines based on common information model," *IEEE Access*, vol. 12, pp. 31 386–31 398, 2024.
- [29] J. V. De Barros and J. B. Leite, "Development of a relational database oriented on the common information model for power distribution net- works," in *2021 IEEE URUCON*, 2021, pp. 63–66.
- [30] W. Zomerdijk, P. Palensky, T. AlSkaif, and P. P. Vergara, "On future power systems digital twins: A vision towards a standard architecture," 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2404.02568>
- [31] MONTI, Antonello et al. A global real-time superlab: Enabling high penetration of power electronics in the electric grid. **IEEE Power Electronics Magazine**, v. 5, n. 3, p. 35-44, 2018.
- [32] MAZZA, Andrea et al. On the model flexibility of the geographical distributed real-time co-simulation: The example of ENET-RT lab. **Sustainable Energy, Grids and Networks**, v. 40, p. 101501, 2024.
- [33] C. Velasco-Gallego and I. Lazakis, "Development of a time series imaging approach for fault classification of marine systems," *Ocean Engineering*, vol. 263, p. 112 297, 2022.
- [34] E. Jakobsson, E. Frisk, M. Krysanter, and R. Pettersson, "Time series fault classification for wave propagation systems with sparse fault data," arXiv preprint arXiv:2203.16121, 2022

- [35] S. Shao, R. Yan, Y. Lu, P. Wang, and R. X. Gao, "Dcnn-based multi-signal induction motor fault diagnosis," *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 69, no. 6, pp. 2658–2669, 2019.
- [36] Q. Song, M. Wang, W. Lai, and S. Zhao, "On Bayesian optimization-based residual CNN for estimation of inter-turn short circuit fault in PMSM," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 38, no. 2, pp. 2456–2468, 2022.
- [37] I. D. Mienye and Y. Sun, "A survey of ensemble learning: Concepts, algorithms, applications, and prospects," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 99 129–99 149, 2022.
- [38] A. Mohammed and R. Kora, "A comprehensive review on ensemble deep learning: Opportunities and challenges," *Journal of King Saud University-Computer and Information Sciences*, vol. 35, no. 2, pp. 757–774, 2023
- [39] M. Haseeb Arshad, H. Wang, J. Yao, Q. Zhao. "Rotor Imbalance Fault Classification Through Unified Feature Fusion: Combining Statistical Signal Processing with Adaptive Deep Learning", submitted to *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, 2024
- [40] J. Pan, Y. Zi, J. Chen, Z. Zhou, and B. Wang, "Liftingnet: A novel deep learning network with layerwise feature learning from noisy mechanical data for fault classification," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 65, no. 6, pp. 4973–4982, 2017
- [41] A. Khan, A. Sohail, U. Zahoora, and A. S. Qureshi, "A survey of the recent architectures of deep convolutional neural networks," *Artificial Intelligence Review*, vol. 53, pp. 5455–5516, 2020
- [42] H. Wang, Y. Li, A. Wijesekera, G. J. Kish, and Q. Zhao, "Switch opencircuit fault detection and localization for modular multilevel converters based on signal synthesis," *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 5391–5404, 2023.
- [43] Q. Yang, J. Qin, and M. Saeedifard, "A postfault strategy to control the modular multilevel converter under submodule failure," *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, vol. 31, no. 6, pp. 2453–2463, 2016.
- [44] S. Farzamkia, H. Iman-Eini, M. Noushak, and A. Hadizadeh, "Improved fault-tolerant method for modular multilevel converters by combined DC and neutral-shift strategy," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 66, no. 3, pp. 2454–2462, 2019.
- [45] A. Rashid, P. Biswas, A. Biswas, M. A. A. Nasim, K. D. Gupta, and R. George, "Present and future of ai in renewable energy domain : A comprehensive survey," 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2406.16965>
- [46] Ö. Baltacı, Z. Kiral, K. Dalkılıç, and O. Karaman, "Thermal image and inverter data analysis for fault detection and diagnosis of PV systems," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 14, no. 9, 2024.
- [47] L. Costa, A. Silva, R. J. Bessa, and R. Araújo, "PV inverter fault classification using machine learning and clarke transformation," in *IEEE PowerTech 2023 Conference*, Belgrade, Serbia, 2023, pp. 1–6.
- [48] J. Van Gompel, D. Spina, and C. Develder, "Neural Network Based Approaches for Fault Diagnosis of Photovoltaic Systems," in *Machine Learning Applications for Intelligent Energy Management*,
- [49] H. Doukas, V. Marinakis, and E. Sarmas, Eds. Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, 2024, vol. 35, pp. 105–129, series Title: Learning and Analytics in Intelligent Systems. [Online]. Available: <https://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-031-47909-04>

- [50] S. Kumar and P. K. Nayak, "An effective method for detection and location estimation of faults in large-scale solar pv arrays," *Solar Energy*, vol. 277, p. 112727, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0038092X24004225>
- [51] S. Rai, P. Kumar, and P. Bajpai, "An integrated approach for fault detection, classification and location in solar pv array," in *2023 10th IEEE International Conference on Power Systems (ICPS)*, 2023, pp. 1–6.
- [52] Retrieved from <https://www.dw.com/en/can-europe-go-carbon-neutral-by-2050/a-46699965>.
- [53] Retrieved from https://lrb.pt/blog_roteiro.php.
- [54] S. RatrengAlessandro Molle P. Udomsamuthirun · T. Kruaehong · T. Nilkamjon and Carlo Grazianetti. Genesys-mod, tu berlin. Retrieved from <https://openentrance.eu/2021/04/27/genesys-mod-tu-berlin/>.
- [55] EU. Going climate - neutral by 2050. Retrieved from https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/climate-strategies-targets/2050-long-term-strategy_en.
- [56] Peter Challenor Jim Q. Smith Victoria Volodina, Nikki Sonenberg. A bayesian decision support system in energy systems planning. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2204.05035>.
- [57] Xiangtian Zheng Yan Liu Mengdi Wang Vijay Vittal P. R. Kumar Srinivas Shakkottai Yi Cui Le Xie, Tong Huang. Energy system digitization in the era of ai: A three-layered approach towards carbon neutrality. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2211.0458>.
- [58] Matteo Giacomo Prina Valeria Casalicchio Giampaolo Manzolini Wolfram Sparber Alice Di Bella, Federico Canti. Power system investment optimization to identify carbon neutrality scenarios for italy. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2311.17443>.
- [59] Detailed Roadmap for the Waterfront Pilot in Ålesund. Authors: Andreas Amundsen (AK), Grete Valen Blindheim (SUAS), Tone-Lise Vilje (SUAS), Report contributors: Allison Wildman (ICLEI), Lies Debbaut (Stad Brugge) <https://re-value-cities.eu/documents/detailed-roadmap-waterfront-pilot-alesund>